

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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REVISION OF ENHANCED RECOVERY AFTER SURGERY PATHWAY
FOLLOWING BLADDER SURGERY

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Radical Cystectomy (RC) is the treatment of choice in muscle invasive urinary bladder cancer (MIBC). However; it carries a high-risk for morbidity and mortality, prolonged length of stay (LOS), and an increase in hospital readmission (RA) rates when compared with other urologic surgical procedures. In an effort to mitigate the morbidity associated with RC, the Enhanced Recovery after Surgery (ERAS) pathway was developed. This clinical pathway guides multi-disciplinary teams in their efforts to improve recovery from RC.

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing (DNP) project was to update the ERAS pathway to include current clinical practice guidelines and improve communication and documentation related to completion of the ERAS pathway. The measured outcomes included: 1) length of stay (LOS) in days, 2) RA within 30 days, 3) patient satisfaction, 4) return of bowel function in relation to decreased incidence of post-op ileus, and 5) incidence of DVT. During the implementation and post-intervention period, there was a reduction in 30-day RA rates, LOS, complications, increases in patient satisfaction and a shorter return of bowel activity post-RC. There were improvements in documentation practices and communication between interdisciplinary team (IDT) members related to the completion of the ERAS pathway. This project was able to develop and rejuvenate a culture of improvement and compliance among IDT members involved in the care of post-RC patients.

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BACKGROUND

The sixth most common cancer in the United States is urinary bladder cancer (UBC) with men more likely to be affected than women (Siegel, Miller, & Jemal, 2015). In 2015, there were 74,000 new cases of UBC affecting 56,320 men and 17,680 women (Siegel et al., 2015). Radical Cystectomy (RC) is the treatment of choice in muscle invasive UBC, however; it carries a high-risk for morbidity and mortality, prolonged length of stay (LOS), and an increase in hospital RA rates when compared with the other urologic surgical procedures (Daneshmand et al., 2014).

In an effort to mitigate the morbidity associated with RC, the project hospital developed the Enhanced Recovery after Surgery (ERAS) pathway. This clinical pathway guides multi-disciplinary teams in their support of improved recovery from RC. A meta-analysis comparing the effectiveness of ERAS to standard care on peri-operative outcomes found that patients experienced fewer complications when the pathway was employed (Tyson & Chang, 2016). The meta-analysis showed that ERAS pathways reduced LOS, decreased post-operative complication rates, and improved bowel function return (Tyson & Chang, 2016). The ERAS pathway provides a standardized method of care, which improves health outcomes and lowers costs due to complications. The ERAS pathway begins at the preoperative phase. Some of the components that the pathway concentrates on include early enteral feeding, avoidance of bowel preparation, and early ambulation. When the patient is discharged to home, the patient is monitored closely via scheduled phone calls and clinic visits.

Problem Statement

The ERAS pathway begins at the preoperative phase with identification of hospital goals of care. The pathway also includes information on post-operative care which focuses on stoma care, early oral feeding, and early mobilization. The patient is monitored closely via scheduled phone calls and clinic visits after discharge to home.

A limitation of the current ERAS pathway is inconsistent documentation of implementation. The lack of a standardized documentation process causes some members of the interdisciplinary team (IDT) to assume that essential components of the ERAS pathway have been implemented. In addition, documentation lapses arise from the processes related to medical training at the facility as well. The training of urology fellows at the project hospital is limited to one year, with weekly rotations on the wards. Since there is a different fellow assigned per week, pathway adherence is difficult to track and inconsistent documentation and communication results in fragmented care. For example, patients on controlled analgesia medications may not be assessed for all aspects of pain control. Occasionally patients are not evaluated for discontinuance of the controlled analgesia medications until discharge. This lack of evaluation causes a delay in timely discharge. In addition, because of prolonged use of analgesia, there is an increased risk of post-operative ileus and constipation.

Some IDT members such as nursing, physical therapy, and pharmacy also have difficulty following the pathway because the existing pathway lacks current clinical practice guidelines (CPG). For example, the pathway includes post-operative deep vein thrombosis prophylaxis. At present, there are no written parameters for changing the recommended anticoagulant to another medication when the serum creatinine clearance

worsens. If current CPG were embedded in the ERAS, nurses could recommend to doctors that they change the anticoagulant when the serum creatinine clearance rises. Thus, integrating established CPG into the ERAS could optimize care and improve patient outcomes (Gustafsson et al., 2011).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing (DNP) project is to update the ERAS pathway to include current clinical practice guidelines and improve communication and documentation related to completion of the ERAS pathway. The DNP project will improve process of care for the management of patients undergoing RC. The aims are: 1) revise the ERAS pathway to integrate clinical EBP guidelines, 2) pilot the revised ERAS pathway, and 3) evaluate the effectiveness of revised ERAS pathway to improve documentation and communication.

SUPPORTING FRAMEWORK

Conceptual frameworks are the foundation that guides scholars in the organization and presentation of ideas. Frameworks provide structure, improve project efficiency, and define interrelated project variables (Varkey et al., 2008).

Logic Model

The Logic Model will guide this project as it provided a method for linking a program's resources, activities, outputs, and its intended outcomes. Furthermore, it facilitated evaluation of the program and allowed for improvements in communication between stakeholders (Lawton et al., 2014). The Logic Model outlined the planning and monitoring of the project as it was implemented and evaluated. First, it is used as a guide in understanding the activities of the program and its intended outcomes. Second, it is utilized to identify evaluation questions (Lawton et al., 2014).

The Logic Model is increasing in popularity for planning and evaluating various types of programs (Fielden et al., 2007). This model is an instrument that guides program design at different stages of implementation and evaluation. Moreover, this model has gained recognition in the healthcare community because of its use among organization and funding agencies (Fielden et al., 2007). Some authors recommend that a project begins with understanding the outcomes and working backwards so the vision guides the development of the inputs and activities required to start the project. Thus, starting with the end in mind allowed the project leader to identify all components of the project and identify barriers before they occur (Fielden et al., 2007). The components of the Logic Model include resources, activities, outputs, short, intermediate, and long-term outcomes, and external influences (McLaughlin & Jordan, 1998). This project has two components,

which can be identified by the processes and outcomes of the ERAS pathway. The process section described the inputs such as resources, activities, and outputs. The outcomes illustrated the intended effects of the program, which can be short-term, intermediate and/or long term. (CDC, n.d.).

Definitions of concepts are as follows:

Input. The resources that go into a program or intervention.

Activities. The events are undertaken by the program to produce the desired outcomes.

Outputs. The direct tangible results of activities are based upon short, intermediate, or long-term objectives. These products served as documentation of progress toward the goals. The outputs were dependent on the objectives, length of the program, expectations, and interventions.

Impact. The influence of the program on the expected outcomes.

Assumptions. The beliefs that guide the development and interventions used in the program, as well as the resources required to implement the program.

Contextual factors. The program setting and the external factors that interact with and influence the program or intervention.

Integration of the Logic Model into the ERAS Pathway Project

The Logic Model guided the project by identifying the process and outcomes of revising the ERAS pathway and integrating CPG. The model provided an effective means for communicating with stakeholders. The model outlined methods for communicating while developing and implementing the objectives of the project. It served as a definitive path of the processes required to guide this project towards the intended outcomes. The

unit nurse managers, physicians, nurses, IDT, and other healthcare providers were involved and supported the plan.

The Logic Model consists of two sections: Process and Outcomes. The Process section demonstrated the Inputs (Resources), Activities and Outputs. The Input included IDT staff, educational materials, time, equipment, and the specialized knowledge and information needed to develop and implement the processes (Lawton et al., 2014). This lead to the final outcomes. The ERAS pathway is based upon current EBP literature. The Clinical Informatics (CI) department provided specialized services and knowledge to integrate the revised ERAS pathway and CPG into the Electronic Health Record (EHR).

Activities include the processes, steps, and actions essential to produce the final results (Lawton et al., 2014). Highly involved training and education sessions for the IDT members occurred. An EBP literature review was conducted to provide the foundation for the development of the clinical practice guidelines, which included the revision of the current ERAS pathway. The CI department facilitated the integration of the revised ERAS pathway and newly developed CPG occurred.

The products of the project activities are called outputs or outcomes. They entail the quantifiable and definitive changes within a period (Lawton et al., 2014). Short-term outcomes included IDT member's demonstration of knowledge and comprehension of the revised ERAS pathway by conducting random chart audits. A standardized method of documenting implementation of the revised ERAS pathway and newly developed CPG occurred. Intermediate outcomes included increased communication between IDT members and improved clinical practices through the utilization of the revised ERAS and CPG.

Long-term outcomes are defined as impact and organizational level changes (Lawton et al., 2014). The outcomes such as decreased length of stay (LOS), complications, and RA rates were monitored at the institutional level one year after implementation. Thus, the Logic Model framework supported the definitions discussed in the project outcomes or outputs. Indicators of quality of care include a decrease in the usage of narcotic pain medications, LOS, complications, and RA (Tyson & Chang, 2016). The CPG improved workflow, decreased reliance on memory, and decreased the incidence of human errors (Vries et al., 2009). It is essential to formulate EBP guidelines to assist providers and IDT members in their decision-making process in the care of post-RC patients. The evidenced-based practice (EBP) guidelines ensured a systematic method for documentation to the ERAS pathway. Figure 1 provides a visual representation of the detailed input, activities, and outputs or outcomes.

Logic Model for Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) Pathway

Project goal: to revise care pathway for post-RC patients.

Figure 1. Revision of the ERAS using the Logic Model.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The literature review consisted of a search for articles pertaining to improved health outcomes utilizing handoff practices and identifying best practices for ERAS. Several key-words were used to search for articles which included decreased LOS, complications, and RAs. Various combinations of the key search terms were utilized during the search. These included Enhanced Recovery after Surgery and ERAS, clinical practice guidelines, radical cystectomy, robotic- assisted, standardized documentation, ERAS implementation, clinical pathways, and fast track.

The search engines PubMed, CINAHL (Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature), Science Direct, PsycInfo, and Google Scholar, were accessed through the California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) and City of Hope (COH) Library databases. In addition, a search was conducted on the databases of the American Urological Association and the European Urological Association for research conducted over the last ten years.

There were a variety of articles selected for the review, which consisted of journals, systematic reviews, randomized control trials, and meta-analyses. The search was limited to peer- reviewed articles from 2007 to present. Articles were excluded if they were duplications, and not relevant to the project based upon titles and topics. Articles that included historical perspectives, abstracts and non-related commentaries were excluded from the literature review.

The review of literature was organized based upon the following topics 1) the components of the ERAS pathway along with recommendations for revisions to include a) urinary drainage, b) prevention of post-operative ileus, c) prevention of post-operative

nausea and vomiting, d) post-operative analgesia, e) early oral diet, f) deep vein thrombosis prophylaxis, and g) early mobilization, 2) review of clinical practice guidelines that will be integrated into a revised pathway, and 3) clinical practice guidelines that improve outcomes, patient satisfaction, and staff satisfaction in their use of the standardized practices. The Table of Evidence (TOE) outlines the topics reviewed for the review of literature and is available in the Appendix I. Appendix I includes articles about the ERAS pathway for improved healthcare outcomes and encompasses articles, which includes post-operative care of RC patients implementing the ERAS components.

Enhanced Recovery after Surgery

Evidence Synthesis

The ERAS pathway aligns patient care to standardized best practices to optimize health outcomes (Tyson & Chang, 2016). Pathways such as the ERAS reduce variations in practice to decrease incidence of errors (Tyson & Chang, 2016). Studies have shown that an integrated multi-disciplinary clinical pathway improves patient outcomes, reduces errors, and increases patient and provider satisfaction (Azhar et al., 2016; Hu et al., 2014; Tyson & Chang, 2014).

A meta-analysis by Tyson and Chang (2016) included thirteen studies and examined the effectiveness of ERAS versus standard care in the reduction of length of stay (LOS), RA rates, complications, and time of bowel activity post-RC. The findings showed that there was a lower rate of RA among patients who received ERAS compared to those who received standard care. In addition, complication rates, LOS, and bowel function improved with the use of the ERAS (Tyson & Chang, 2016).

The concept of ERAS was first introduced in the 1990s in the field of colorectal surgery with the goal of improving recovery after surgery and shortening LOS. At present, RC is frequently associated with high rates of complications, morbidity, and prolonged LOS despite significant improvements in care (Collins et al., 2016). The aim of the modern ERAS pathway is to have a positive impact on healthcare outcomes and patient care in terms of diagnosis, peri-operative period, and return to normal function. However, there continues to be a lack of the availability of high level evidence and disbelief of some cystectomy surgeons in the ERAS concepts (Collins et al., 2016). Many of the principles applied to the ERAS pathway in post-RC patients have been imported from colorectal surgery (Collins et al., 2016).

Thus, the need for rigorous and well-designed studies in assessing the impact of ERAS on post-RC is necessary. There is considerable variability in the adoption of ERAS principles and a significant gap between the application of the ERAS pathway principles and physician perception (Kukreja et al., 2016). These findings provide an important opportunity to make a difference in the quality of care for post-RC patients (Kukreja et al., 2016).

Early Mobilization

The literature provides support that pre-habilitation is an essential element to improve patient outcomes and decrease post-operative morbidity (Jensen et al., 2016; Gillis et al., 2014; Mayo et al., 2011). In an RCT study conducted by Jensen et al., (2016) there were 107 patients divided into two groups, the intervention group consisted of 50 patients, and the control group had 57. The intervention group received standardized pre-operative and post-operative strengthening, and endurance exercises, along with dynamic

post-operative mobilization. The program was instituted two weeks prior to RC. Efficacy was measured in terms of outcomes such as reduction in post-operative LOS, and complications. This RCT demonstrated that pre-habilitation was significant and led to improvements in physical capacity. Thus, early ambulation lead to significant positive health outcomes and early recovery (Jensen et al., 2016; Gillis et al., 2014; Mayo et al., 2011).

Several studies have shown that there are similar results in the overall increase in functional capacity, quality of life improvement, patient outcome improvement, and reduction of post-operative morbidity when early mobilization is implemented (Jensen et al., 2016; Jones et al., 2010; Porsrud at al., 2014). Cerantola and associates (2013) made recommendations to encourage early ambulation of post- RC patients at least two hours out of bed on post-operative day (POD) zero and six hours out of bed on POD one. The recommendation is strongly based on the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) system. Moreover, the consensus view of the European Association of Urology (EAU) scientific working group, which was comprised of experts from high volume robotic assisted radical cystectomy (RARC) hospitals in Europe reached a 100 percent consensus regarding early ambulation. This recommendation also aids in the reduction of post-operative pain (Collins et al., 2016). The current ERAS pathway is operationalized as an order set at the project hospital (see Appendix C). The ERAS order set needs to be modified and a guideline is needed that includes patients being taken out of bed at least two hours on POD zero and six hours out of bed on POD one, unless contraindicated as supported by the studies discussed. The

need for this update was supported by a strong recommendation under the GRADE system.

DVT Prophylaxis

Studies have shown that patients undergoing abdominal and pelvic cancer surgeries are prone to Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT) (Geerts et al., 2008; Nomura et al., 2013). Thus, it is important to implement DVT prophylaxis in patients undergoing abdominal and pelvic cancer surgeries (Geerts et al., 2008; Nomura et al., 2013). Low Molecular Weight Heparin (LMWH) has been recommended as the drug of choice for DVT prophylaxis by surgeons who manage post-RC surgical patients as it is more effective, safe, and convenient with a once- daily dosing regimen (Geerts et al., 2008; Nomura et al., 2013). Moreover, studies have shown that Low- Density Heparin (LDH) and LMWH are equally adequate for DVT prophylaxis during abdominal surgery (Geerts et al., 2008; Nomura et al., 2013).

In a study conducted by Pariser et al. (2015), a new regimen of thromboprophylaxis for post-RC patients was implemented using an extended administration of Enoxaparin, an LMWH, which was administered for 28 days after discharge. The LMWH or Enoxaparin regimen demonstrated a decrease in VTE cases (12 % vs. 5%, $p = .024$) and a significant reduction of VTE events after discharge (six vs. two percent, $p = .039$). Multivariate analysis showed a reduction of VTE cases upon implementation of the LMWH or Enoxaparin regimen ($p = .009$). Thus, the extended Enoxaparin regimen post-RC was shown to decrease the rate of VTE events after discharge compared to inpatients who only received Heparin in the absence of bleeding risk (Pariser et al.,

2015). A healthcare provider's determination for the use of either LDH or LMWH is dependent upon the patient's renal function (Geerts et al., 2008; Nomura et al., 2013).

The Practice Guidelines Committee of the American Urological Association (AUA) created a panel to develop the Best Practice Statement for DVT prophylaxis of patients scheduled to undergo urologic surgery. The best practice statement was developed by abstracting published data along with the opinion from experts and clinical practice physicians (Forrest et al., 2009). The Summary of VTE recommendations was based on patient risk stratification. Since post-RC patients are classified as high or highest risk, the focus of the recommendations targeted these groups. The high-risk groups include patients older than 60, scheduled for surgery or age 40 to 60 with other risk factors such as the history of venous thromboembolism (VTE), hypercoagulability, and cancer patients. The VTE Prophylaxis recommendations were comprised of 1) Heparin 5,000 units subcutaneously every eight hours to start after surgery, 2) Enoxaparin 40mg subcutaneously daily if creatinine clearance is over 30 ml/min or 30 mg if the creatinine clearance is less than 30 ml/minute, 3) pneumatic compression device if high risk for bleeding. (Forrest et al., 2009; Geerts et al., 2008; Nomura et al., 2013). The highest risk groups include diagnosis of cancer, older than 40, and history of VTE. The recommendations were the same as the high-risk groups combined with pneumatic compression devices (Forrest et al., 2009). A healthcare provider's determination for the use of either LDH or LMWH is dependent upon the patient's renal function (Geerts et al., 2008; Nomura et al., 2013). The level of evidence is high, and the recommendation grade is strong based on the GRADE system.

The current ERAS order sets at the project hospital does not include pharmacologic recommendations on appropriate dosage based on serum creatinine clearance parameters. There is a need to include a guideline to the ERAS order set at the project hospital to address dosage adjustments or changes to other anticoagulants. These adjustments need to be based on the patient's serum creatinine clearance levels when administering an LMWH. The need to update this component is supported by the high quality of evidence and strong recommendation grade given by the GRADE system.

A systematic review was conducted based on available published data regarding the cost- effectiveness, safety, and efficacy of extended duration of VTE prophylaxis. Studies have found that use of extended duration of DVT prophylaxis by incorporating a 28-45-day LMWH regimen can decrease the risk of developing VTE among high-risk patients. In separate meta-analyses, there was decreased incidence in the development of VTE compared to the one-week standard duration regimen (Huo & Muntz, 2009; Kanaan et al., 2007). The recommendation presented and discussed by Cerantola et al., (2013) showed a high level of evidence to support the use of one-month duration regime of LMWH along with the use of intermittent pneumatic compression devices.

Prevention of Post-Operative Ileus

Radical Cystectomy is frequently related to delayed recovery of gastrointestinal (GI) function that extends unnecessary LOS. Lee et al., (2014) conducted a randomized double-blind placebo-controlled study among patients undergoing RC. The intervention group of patients received oral Alvimopan with a 12- milligram maximum dose divided into 15 doses. Studies have shown that Alvimopan is beneficial for patients undergoing

RC because it accelerates return of bowel function and shortens LOS compared with those who received a placebo (Lee et al., 2014).

Choi et al. (2011) conducted a randomized clinical trial (RCT) to determine whether chewing gum facilitated the return of bowel function among post-RC patients. In the study, there were 60 participants divided into the non-gum chewing and gum chewing groups. The outcome demonstrated that the time for flatus and bowel movement was shorter in the gum chewing (GC) group at 12 hours versus 16 hours for the non-gum chewing group ($p < .01$). The recommendation formulated from current evidence recommended gum chewing every hour from POD one to seven in combination with the use of Alvimopan 12mg to facilitate earlier return of bowel function, shorten LOS, and reduce hospital costs (Cerantola et al., 2013; Collins et al., 2016). The evidence level is moderate, and the recommendation grade is strong. The study showed robust evidence that chewing gum stimulates bowel motility after RC and urinary diversion. Studies have shown that gum chewing enhanced and promoted intestinal functioning and faster return to bowel function post-RC. The evidence exhibited that chewing gum was safe and could be used to reduce incidence of post-operative ileus (Choi et al., 2011).

The current ERAS order sets need to be modified to include the duration of gum chewing specifically seven days post-RC. In addition, the current ERAS order set is implementing the recommendation on Entereg also known as Alvimopan 12 milligram orally two times daily for five days or 10 doses. A guideline that states that a maximum of 15 doses is allowed and should be specifically written in the order set. This guideline supported the current literature regarding the benefits and maximum allowable dosage of administration of Alvimopan 12 mg post-RC.

Post-Operative Analgesia

Current studies have shown that Acetaminophen and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDS) are commonly recommended for analgesia among patients undergoing RC. The latter has recently been questioned in reports due to increased incidence of anastomotic leaks (Cerantola et al., 2013; Maffezzini et al., 2012; Torren et al., 2009). Studies have recommended that Acetaminophen and NSAIDS are good baseline treatment options for post-operative pain. There are no prospective data that suggests that opioid sparing multi-modal pain concepts can be safely adopted in major urologic surgical procedures including RC (Cerantola et al., 2013; Maffezzini et al., 2012; Torren et al., 2009).

The EAU robotic section scientific working group reached a 100% consensus and recommended standardized poly-pharmacologic opioid sparing analgesia. Baseline treatment includes intravenous (IV) acetaminophen if the patient is unable to tolerate oral intake. It was also recommended to avoid epidural analgesia to promote early mobilization (Collins et al., 2016). The evidence level is high, and the recommendation grade is strong under the GRADE system. The current ERAS order sets at the project hospital followed the recommendations that IV Acetaminophen or IV NSAIDS should be administered first prior to initiation of PCA analgesia on POD one. A guideline was included with supporting evidence that showed the benefits of using IV Acetaminophen or IV NSAIDS as baseline treatment for post-operative pain.

Early Oral Diet

Normal oral food intake was considered an essential component of the ERAS pathway to maintain body homeostasis (Cerantola et al., 2013). Studies have shown that

an early oral diet has similar results in terms of decreased time to first bowel movement, stimulation of GI function, and decrease LOS without increasing the rate of complications. (Collins et al., 2016; Karl et al., 2009; Nygren et al., 2013).

The European Association of Urology (EAU) scientific panel reached a 96 % consensus and recommended that early oral feeding should be initiated early as tolerated by post-RC patients avoiding parenteral nutrition (Collins et al., 2016). Studies have shown that a normal diet as opposed to parenteral nutrition should be encouraged and re-established as soon as four hours after RC. The evidence level is moderate, and the recommendation grade is high. There is lack of evidence that prolonged fasting after RC can reduce the incidence of post-operative ileus (Cerantola et al., 2013; Collins et al., 2016).

The current ERAS order sets were modified in terms of adding a guideline that showed the most recent evidence of starting oral feeding at least four hours after RC. A recommendation to start daily nutritional supplements along with a nutritional goal of 900 kcal per day from POD two to four, 1500 kcal per day from POD four and onwards, and fluid and electrolytes at 30 ml/kg daily was included in the guideline. This was included in the current ERAS at the project hospital as recommended by the study conducted by Collins et al., (2016). The strength of the recommendation was strong, and the evidence level was moderate according to the GRADE system (Collins et al., 2016).

Urinary Drainage

Studies have shown that early removal of the transurethral urinary catheter can reduce the incidence of urinary tract infections in abdominal and thoracic surgical procedures (Collins et al., 2016; Cerantola et al., 2013). An RCT conducted by Collins et

al. (2016) showed that a 71% consensus was reached by the European Association of Urology (EAU) robotic urology scientific working group regarding the optimal timing of orthoptic neobladder catheter removal. The EAU committee members recommended keeping the catheter for at least fourteen days' post-discharge. The ERAS order set at the project hospital is currently following the recommendation to remove the catheter in orthoptic neobladder urinary diversions three weeks' post-discharge. A formally written CPG on optimal timing for removing the catheter is at least 14 days' post-discharge, which was included in the discharge instructions of the ERAS order set as recommended by the Collins et al. (2016) study.

Prevention of Post-Operative Nausea and Vomiting

Studies recommended a multi-modal anti-emetic prophylactic approach for patients at high risk for post-operative nausea and vomiting (Jellish et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2015). Moreover, studies have shown evidence and similar results that intra-operative stenting of the uretero-ileal anastomosis site and fluid monitoring revealed a reduction of post-operative nausea and vomiting. (Cerantola et al., 2013; Collins et al., 2016; Wilhelm et al., 2007).

A meta-analysis by Wang et al., (2015) compared Dexamethasone to Ondansetron in the prevention of post-operative nausea and vomiting in patients scheduled for laparoscopic surgery. The effectiveness of the multi-modal anti-emetic approach with the use of Ondansetron and Dexamethasone was supported by the meta-analysis. The analysis concluded Dexamethasone was more effective from six to 24 hours while Ondansetron was more effective in the first six-hours post-operatively. The evidence level is high, and the recommendation grade is strong according to the GRADE system.

Collins et al. (2016) recommended prevention of post-operative nausea and vomiting as an important component of the ERAS pathway.

The current ERAS order set has Ondansetron 4mg IV every six hours as needed for nausea and vomiting on POD zero to one. There is a need for this ERAS component to be updated and to include a guideline that incorporates the administration of Ondansetron in the first six hours' post-operative and add Dexamethasone six hours' post-operative as needed to prevent nausea and vomiting. This was based on current clinical practice guidelines and evidence. The need to update this ERAS component was supported by the strong recommendation given by the GRADE system.

The Five ERAS Components

The present project implemented five of the seven ERAS components. The five components are DVT prophylaxis, prevention of post-operative ileus, early mobilization, early oral feeding, and post-operative pain management. These components were reviewed for their significance in improving health outcomes after RC. Each component was examined for its strength of research evidence and influence to affect patient care using the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) system. This system classified each ERAS component as high, moderate, low, or very low based upon the quality of the research available for review. A high rating indicated that additional research did not change the confidence in the outcome of the benefit of the ERAS component. A moderate rating means additional research may have changed the confidence in the outcome of the benefit of the ERAS component. A low rating indicated that additional research impacted the confidence in the outcome and had the desired effects. A very low rating indicated that additional research would highly

influence the confidence in the benefit of the ERAS component and warrant removal of it from the pathway. The GRADE system provides a method for separating quality of the research from strength of the recommendations to use the ERAS component. An ERAS component was rated high when the research supporting its use was high and the outcome was positive. However, when the quality was low, and the outcome was negative, the quality would be very low. Table 1 provides an overview of each ERAS component, which was implemented in this project along with its GRADE score.

Table 1

The Five ERAS Components and Level of Confidence and Recommendation

ERAS Component	Overview	RARC Relevance	Confidence Level	Recommendation
DVT prophylaxis	Compression stockings w/ LMWH. 4 weeks extended prophylaxis for high risk patients	Cystectomy patients are high risk & need prolonged prophylaxis	High	Strong
Prevention of post-operative ileus	Gum chewing to optimize GI function		Moderate	Strong
Early mobilization	Early mobilization encouraged	2 hours out of bed on POD 0; 6 hours out of bed POD 1	Low	Strong
Early oral feeding	Should start 4 hours after surgery		Moderate	Strong
Post-operative pain management	Multi-modal post-operative analgesia		High	Strong

Clinical Practice Guidelines

Studies have shown that there are significant improvements when there is compliance with EBP CPG as well as in short-term LOS, complication rates, and financial outcomes (Kredo et al., 2016). A comprehensive summary of randomized

control trials was conducted and evaluated the significance of implementing clinical decision support systems or CPG that included the following features: 1) clinical decision support as a workflow component, 2) informatics technology based to generate the decision support, 3) actionable recommendations provided at the time of delivery and 4) site where decision making made. Moreover, clinical support systems or CPG have shown to reduce medical errors and improve patient care (Kredo et al., 2016).

Documentation Improvement

A systematic review conducted by Rathert et al., (2017) provided an extensive investigation of the electronic health record (EHR) documenting its influence on communication effectiveness and impact on patient outcomes. Future EHRs can be developed to facilitate better patient- centered care by emphasizing the role of communication in patient healthcare outcomes. Some clinicians collaborated with their patients by sharing their information using the EHR, but typically the EHR was in a place where clinicians were forced to leave their patients to enter data (Rathert et al., 2017). Overall patient-centeredness can be improved by making the EHR easy to share while allowing more time for clinicians to interact with their patients (Rathert et al., 2017). Furthermore, EHR documentation enhanced communication. The provider incentives included improved patient outcomes in comparison to merely being rewarded for using specific features in the EHR (Rather et al., 2017).

Evaluation of Effect on Documentation

Systematic reviews conducted by Cerantola et al. (2013) have shown that audit and feedback lead to improvements in healthcare outcomes. Auditing compliance is an essential factor for successful implementation of the ERAS pathway and its principles. In

addition, the study mentioned that there were four significant roles of auditing compliance. These included: 1) clinical outcome measurements such as LOS, morbidity, RA rates within 30 days, and post-operative ileus, 2) measurement of non-clinical healthcare outcomes such as costs and patient satisfaction, 3) measurement of compliance or adherence to the ERAS, 4) philosophy of dynamic evolution of new available evidence, and readiness to modify the multi-modal concepts of ERAS if needed (Cerantola et al., 2013). Moreover, a study conducted by Patel et al., (2014) emphasized the importance of a standardized method for documentation and measurement of clinical outcomes. This will yield the most reliable and highest level of evidence.

In conclusion, based on the evidence and the literature reviews, the ERAS and integration of CPG have shown to deliver dependable and high- quality standardized services within an interdisciplinary working environment. The guidance on standardized post RC care can improve healthcare outcomes. The key principles include patient education during the peri-operative period, nutrition optimization, early mobilization, post-operative pain management, anti-emetic regimens, DVT prophylaxis, and robotic-assisted radical cystectomy surgical techniques.

However, there is lack of agreement regarding which ERAS components need to be integrated and how to provide optimal care across institutions. There is a lack of training and knowledge on which ERAS elements fit best with which type of urological surgery (Di Rollo et al., 2015). The ERAS will continue to evolve in terms of standardization of care and documentation. It requires continued incorporation of the essential components for quality improvement in post-RC care. Thus, the need to conduct this DNP project was supported by the research presented in this literature review.

METHODS

This is a Quality Improvement (QI) project designed to update the ERAS pathway to include the current CPG, as well as improve communication and documentation related to ERAS pathway completion. The project was designed in four phases: 1) planning (input), 2) development (output), 3) implementation and adoption (outcome), and 4) sustainability (long- term outcomes).

Setting

The project took place in two medical- surgical telemetry (MST) floors at a large tertiary cancer center located in the San Gabriel Valley in California. The hospital had 217 beds and had over 300 healthcare providers. The MST floors have 70 monitored beds. The two MST floors were staffed by 100 registered nurses (RNs), 50 certified nursing assistants (CNA), two assistant unit nurse managers, and two-unit nurse managers. The urology service consisted of eight urologists, three urology fellows, one care coordinator, one case manager, one urology in-patient nurse practitioner, one social worker, ten physical therapists, three nutritionists, six-unit secretaries, and seven pharmacists. The MST serves post-surgical cancer patients.

Sample

The sample included all urology in-patients with a diagnosis of muscle- invasive bladder cancer (MIBC), who had undergone robotic assisted radical cystectomy (RARC) from August 2016 to November 2016 and August 2017 to November 2017. Patients younger than 50 were not included in the project. In MIBC, the cancer incidence rate was twenty percent higher in men than in women. Moreover, bladder cancer, the sixth most common cancer in the United States is diagnosed at a median age of 65 years and rarely

diagnosed in individuals younger than 40 years of age (Siegel, Miller, & Jemal, 2015). The project consisted of data pulled randomly from 20 patient charts (ten males and ten females). The inclusion criteria of the random patient charts required that the patient be 50 years or older and had undergone RARC from August through November 2016. The sample included another 20 patients using the same inclusion criteria with charts pulled from August 2017 to November 2017. This sample was compared to the initial sample pulled to compare the results of the intervention.

Ethical Considerations

All IDT members were provided an overview of the project to obtain their consent to participate in the implementation of the CPG and the ERAS pathway. The IDT members provided written consent to indicate their approval to participate in the project. Patients were identified, and data were collected from the EHR. All patient data were de-identified, and records maintained on a password protected computer belonging to the DNP author. The project was reviewed by two Institutional Review Boards (IRB); one from the project hospital, a tertiary cancer center and the other from California State University, Los Angeles. The project hospital's and California State University, Los Angeles' IRB decided the project did not meet the definition of research according to Federal Regulations 45 CFR 46 (Appendix E and F). This DNP project met and complied with all requirements of the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability (HIPPA). Thus, the DNP author moved forward with the quality improvement project.

Project Design and Procedures

The project is an EBP quality improvement project designed to review and revise the ERAS pathway and improve documentation of care processes.

Planning (Input)

On January 19, 2017, the DNP author began an initial review of the literature on ERAS and the CPG. In addition, the 2014 ERAS pathway used in the project setting was reviewed to determine if there was a need for the pathway to be updated. The 2014 ERAS pathway is in the form of physician order set that lists five components: 1) early ambulation on a post-operative day (POD) one, 2) initiation of DVT pharmacologic prophylaxis on POD one, unless contraindicated, 3) post-operative pain management using opioid- sparing analgesia and discontinuing opioid analgesic medication on POD three, 4) early oral feeding within 24 hours, unless contraindicated, and 5) prevention of post-operative ileus by nurse- initiated patient gum chewing every hour and administration of Alvimopan 12mg on POD one, unless contraindicated. The five components of the 2014 ERAS were identified as routine order sets. A retrospective chart review was conducted to determine whether the ERAS patients received each of the 2014 ERAS order sets covered in the five components (see Appendix A).

The data collected from this retrospective chart review was used as a baseline to determine which, if any of the five components were rendered. Data entry was performed by the DNP author using an EXCEL spreadsheet (see Appendix C). The rationale of performing retrospective chart audits and establishing baseline data was to determine if the five ERAS components were performed. This information was used to determine which components were missing and guide the development of a re-education plan for the staff as part of the implementation of the revised ERAS pathway. Retrospective patient satisfaction surveys were collected to determine if there was a difference in patient satisfaction once the 2017 ERAS components were implemented. This data was

stored on a password-protected computer and was only accessible to the DNP author and IDT project development team members.

Development (Output)

In January 2017, a partnership with the Clinical Informatics department was initiated with regards to supporting a web-based design for integrating the CPG into the 2014 ERAS pathway. In May 2017, the DNP author conducted a proposal defense which initiated approval to begin the project. In June 2017 to August 2017, the Institutional Review Board (IRB) application at the project hospital and Cal State LA was initiated. The revision of ERAS and integration of CPG into the current ERAS order set began with the scheduling of bi-weekly urology in-service and IDT staff meetings.

These staff meetings were scheduled using the Outlook calendar in the current electronic database. Upon permission of the unit managers, flyers were posted in the unit conference rooms at the project MST floors. In addition, e-mail reminders were sent to the staff one week prior to the scheduled in-service training sessions. A series of four in-service meetings were held to discuss the revisions of the ERAS pathway to include the CPG. The in-service training sessions were 30 to 60 minutes and were in power-point presentation format. Lecture handouts were provided during the educational training sessions. A 10-item pre-test and post-test questionnaire were administered during each in-service session (see Appendix E). The target audience included staff RNs who worked on the MST floors, physical therapists, unit pharmacists, care coordinator, unit nurse managers, and discharge planners.

Implementation and Adoption (Outcomes)

The revision of the 2014 ERAS to include the CPG was a team effort involving the DNP author, pain management specialist, and nurse care coordinator. The review of literature was conducted, and best practices identified. The framework for the CPG used the format for content, review and rating of the evidence suggested by the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ, n.d.). When the CPG development team reached a consensus on the framework, it was sent for further review and approval by the urology division chief, and quality improvement director.

Upon approval by all necessary hospital stakeholders, continuing in-services and training of IDT members took place. The in-services and training sessions were completed by August 1, 2017. At that time, the first random chart review dated from August 2016 to November 2016 was conducted by the DNP author.

In August 2017 to September 2017, the CPG and the 2017 ERAS components were implemented, integrated, and launched into the EHR and integrated under policy and procedure. The EPIC EHR has the capacity of alerting healthcare providers and IDT members in the form of “Reminder flags” of missing pieces of information. The rationale of having the “Reminder flags” activated was to assure that all components of the 2017 ERAS pathway were documented and completed. Moreover, the new EPIC EHR had the capability to click on the website which was aligned with each 2017 ERAS component that led to current literature regarding the evidence to support its use.

The 2017 ERAS was evaluated on an on-going basis to determine its effectiveness and the need for modification based on feedback from the IDT members and urologists. Participating patients leaving the unit were given a survey.

The short-term outcome measurements included: 1) increased IDT understanding and knowledge of updated ERAS and CPG, 2) user satisfaction regarding the ease in following CPG and, 3) increased adherence and standard documentation completion. Improvements were measured using the scores of the pre-test and the post-test after each of the in-service training sessions. The assessment of knowledge and completion of the five selected components of the 2017 ERAS pathway with the CPG were recorded on an EXCEL spreadsheet. The five selected components included: 1) update on DVT prophylaxis by following the serum creatinine clearance parameters, duration and type of anticoagulant, 2) update for prevention of post-operative ileus in terms of hourly gum chewing in the first seven days post-operatively, and administration of Alvimopan 12mg on POD one unless contraindicated, 3) update on early mobilization that was physical therapist and nurse driven, and implemented in the first 72 hours post-operatively, 4) early oral feeding within 24 hours included daily nutritional supplements and a goal of 900 kcal per day on POD two to POD four, 1500 kcal per day on POD four and onwards, and fluid and electrolytes at 30 ml/kg per day unless contraindicated, 5) update on post-operative pain management by administration of IV Acetaminophen or Ibuprofen and discontinuance of the PCA on POD two, unless contraindicated.

Sustainability (Long-term Outcomes)

In December 2017, a second random chart review of 20 patients who underwent RARC from August 2017 to November 2017 was conducted to determine if implementation of CPG and the updated 2017 ERAS components showed improvements in outcomes. The patient satisfaction survey data was gathered and entered into the

EXCEL spreadsheet. This allowed comparison to patient satisfaction surveys gathered during the pre-2017 ERAS component implementation.

Data Analysis

Data collected during the pre-and post-intervention periods were used to compare effectiveness of the quality improvement project initiative. In January 2018, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 22.0 was utilized for statistical analysis completion. Frequency distribution tables and graphs were used to illustrate completion and non-completion of ERAS components, outcomes in the pre-and post-intervention periods, and percentages of patient satisfaction in the pre-and post-intervention periods.

The metrics analyzed were comprised of data collection regarding LOS based on the number of hospital days, RA rates within 30- day post-discharge, which were measured in percentages, and patient satisfaction based on press-ganey results. The DNP author and a nurse research assistant completed the data documentation and input it into Excel. This data was requested from the project hospitals' quality improvement analyst department head and clinical informatics. Data was compared between the 2014 ERAS and 2017 ERAS pathway to evaluate the effectiveness of the project initiative. Graphs and frequency tables were used to compare the 2014 ERAS without the CPG and the post-RARC group who received the updated 2017 ERAS with current CPGs. The measured outcomes included: 1) LOS in days, 2) RA within 30 days, 3) patient satisfaction, 4) return of bowel function in relationship to decreased incidence of post-op ileus, and 5) incidence of DVT. Adherence with the ERAS components were evaluated

by conducting a quarterly chart analysis. Adherence was calculated for the duration of the implementation of the 2017 ERAS and for each chronological quarter.

Project Product

The final product for this DNP project was an updated 2017 ERAS pathway operationalized in the form of order sets (see Appendix B) to include the current CPG recommendations (see Appendix D), and improve documentation related to the completion of the ERAS pathway. These recommendations assisted healthcare providers and staff in their decision-making process during the care of post-RARC patients. The CPG developed was evaluated and assessed before the project concluded with a peer review and consultation from the experts in the fields of pharmacy, pain management, urology, nutrition, physical therapy, and nursing.

RESULTS: PROJECT MANUSCRIPT

This chapter presents the results of the project before and after implementation of the updated 2017 ERAS pathway, survey results, and outcomes. The pre-intervention period was August 1, 2016 to November 30, 2016 and the post-intervention period was August 1, 2017 to November 30, 2017. The data were abstracted through 20 random chart reviews. Table 2 and 3 show the demographics and include age, gender, and ethnicity. The mean age in years in the pre-and post-intervention period was 68 to 70 years. There were 85 % and 90 % males and 10% and 15 % females in the pre-and post-intervention period, respectively. The samples consisted of 90 % Caucasians and 10 % Asians. The outcomes of the project included: 1) decrease in LOS, 2) decrease in RA rates, 3) decrease incidence of DVT, 4) decrease incidences of post-operative ileus, and 5) increase patient satisfaction through press- ganey survey results. Registered nurses, care coordinators, physical therapists, nutritionists, and urology fellows were the members of the interdisciplinary team in completing the five ERAS components during this project.

Table 2

Demographics among Post-RARC Patients: Pre-Intervention Period (August – November 2016)

	August	September	October	November	N (%)	Mean
Average age (years)	65	70	68	71		68
Gender						
Male	5	6	3	3	17(85%)	
Female	2	0	1	0	3(15%)	
Ethnicity						
Caucasian	7	5	3	3	18(90%)	
Asian	0	1	1	0	2(10%)	

Table 3

Demographics among Post-RARC Patients: Post-Intervention Period (August – November 2017)

	August	September	October	November	N (%)	Mean
Average age (years)	66	72	70	74		70
Gender						
Male	6	6	3	3	18(90%)	
Female	0	1	0	1	2(10%)	
Ethnicity						
Caucasian	6	6	3	3	18 (90%)	
Asian	0	1	0	1	2 (10%)	

Table 4 and Figure 2 show the number and percentages for the completion of the five ERAS pathway components and outcomes before and after intervention. There was an increase in completion rates for the five ERAS components. These included: 1) early mobilization on POD one - from 17(85%) pre-intervention to 19(95%) post-intervention, 2) DVT on POD two – from 16(80%) during the pre-intervention to 18(90%) in the post-intervention period, 3) post-operative analgesia POD one- from 7(35%) to 18(90%) in the post-intervention, and 4) early oral feeding, POD one – from 13(65%) to 19 (95%), and 5) prevention of post-operative ileus, POD one- from 13(65%) to 19(95%).

Table 4

Number and Percentage of Completion and Non- Completion of the Five ERAS Components from 20 random chart reviews: Pre-and Post-Interventions

August to November 2016 Data Abstraction: Pre-Intervention					
Early Mobilization POD1	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Completed	6	5	4	2	17(85)
Not Completed	1	1	0	1	3(15)
August to November 2017 Data Abstraction: Post-Intervention					
Early Mobilization POD1	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Completed	6	6	3	4	19(95)
Not Completed	0	1	0	0	1(5)
August to November 2016 Data Abstraction: Pre-Intervention					
DVT Prophylaxis POD 2	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Completed	4	5	4	3	16(80)
Not Completed	3	1	0	0	4(20)
August to November 2017 Data Abstraction: Post-Intervention					
DVT Prophylaxis POD 2	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Completed	6	7	2	3	18(90)
Not Completed	0	0	1	1	2(10)
August to November 2016 Data Abstraction: Pre-Intervention					
Post-Op Analgesia POD 1	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Completed	2	1	2	2	7(35)
Not Completed	5	5	2	1	13(65)
August to November 2017 Data Abstraction: Post-Intervention					
Post-Op Analgesia POD 1	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Completed	5	6	3	4	18(90)
Not Completed	1	1	0	0	2(10)
August to November 2016 Data Abstraction: Pre-Intervention					
Early Oral Feeding POD1	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Completed	4	5	2	2	13(65)
Not Completed	3	1	2	1	7(35)
August to November 2017 Data Abstraction: Post-Intervention					
Early Oral Feeding POD1	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Completed	6	7	2	4	19(95)
Not Completed	0	0	1	0	1(5)
August to November 2016 Data Abstraction: Pre-Intervention					
Post-Op Ileus POD 1	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Completed	4	5	2	2	13(65)
Not Completed	3	1	2	1	7(35)
August to November 2017 Data Abstraction: Post-Intervention					
Post-Op Ileus POD 1	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Completed	6	6	3	4	19(95)
Not Completed	0	1	0	0	1(5)

Note: POD = Post-Operative Day.

Figure 2. Percentage of completion/non-completion: August to November 2016 and August to November 2017.

Table 5 and Figure 3 show the outcome measures based on the completion of the five ERAS pathway components. The RA numbers and percentages are defined as a re-admission within 30 days of discharge post-operatively. There was a decrease in RA numbers and percentage from 6(30 %) during the pre-intervention period to 1(5%) during the post-intervention period. The non- RA numbers and percentage increased from 14(70 %) during the pre-intervention period to 19(95%) during the post-intervention period. Post-operative ileus decreased from 50% to 10 %. The incidence of the absence of ileus or return of bowel function after post-RARC showed an increase from 10(50%) to 18(90%) during the post-intervention period. The number of DVT cases dropped from three cases after 2017 ERAS implementation. Thus, a notable improvement from 85 % to 100 % was evident in the post-intervention period in terms of absence of DVT.

Table 5

Average Number and Percentage of Outcomes Measured in the Pre- and Post-Intervention period

August to November 2016 Data Abstraction: Pre-Intervention					
Readmission w/in 30 days	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Readmitted	1	5	0	0	6(30)
Not Readmitted	6	1	4	3	14(70)
August to November 2017 Data Abstraction: Post-Intervention					
Readmission w/in 30 days	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Readmitted	0	1	0	0	1(5)
Not Readmitted	6	6	3	4	19(95)
August to November 2016 Data Abstraction: Pre-Intervention					
Return of Bowel Function	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Ileus	4	3	2	1	10(50)
No Ileus	3	3	2	2	10(50)
August to November 2017 Data Abstraction: Post-Intervention					
Return of Bowel Function	August	September	October	November	N (%)
Ileus	0	0	1	1	2(10)
No Ileus	6	7	2	3	18(90)
August to November 2016 Data Abstraction: Pre-Intervention					
DVT	August	September	October	November	N (%)
(+) DVT	2	0	1	0	3(15)
(-) DVT	5	6	3	3	17(85)
August to November 2017 Data Abstraction: Post-Intervention					
DVT	August	September	October	November	N (%)
(+) DVT	0	0	0	0	0(0)
(-) DVT	6	7	3	4	20(100)

Figure 3. Percentage of outcomes: Pre (August to November 2016) and post (August to November 2017) intervention

Table 6 and Figure 4 show the average LOS between the pre-intervention and post-intervention period. There is a decrease in the average LOS in days from 11.5 days during the pre-intervention period to 5.5 days during the post-intervention period.

Table 6

Average Length of Stay (LOS) in days: Pre-/Post-Intervention Period

LOS (Days)	August	September	October	November	Average (Days)
2016	10	12	13	11	11.5
2017	6	5	5	6	5.5

Figure 4. Length of stay (days) pre- and post-intervention.

Table 7 and Figure 5 show the press-ganey survey results of patients who underwent RARC and were rendered the five components of the ERAS pathway components during the pre-intervention period (August 2016 to November 2016) and post-intervention period (August 2017 to November 2017). There was a significant increase in percentage of overall patient satisfaction regarding their care as evidenced by an increase from 84% in the pre-intervention to 92% in the post-intervention period.

Table 7

Percentage of Overall Patient Satisfaction: Press Ganey Survey Results among 20 Post – RARC patients: Pre-and Post-Intervention

Press-ganey	August	September	October	November
2016	80	88	82	86
2017	90	94	92	90

Figure 5. Percentage of Press-Ganey in Post-RARC patients: Pre (August to November 2016) and post-intervention (August to November 2017)

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this DNP project was to update the ERAS pathway to include current CPGs and improve documentation and communication related to the ERAS pathway components. Abstraction of data through 20 random chart reviews from August 1, 2016 to November 30, 2016 (pre-intervention) and August 1, 2017 to November 30, 2017 (post-intervention) were evaluated and compared through project outcomes. These outcomes included: 1) decrease LOS, 2) decrease RA, 3) decrease incidence of DVT, 4) return of bowel function manifested by the absence of post-operative ileus, and 5) increase patient satisfaction in their overall care post-RARC.

The implementation of the CPG and revision of the ERAS pathway improved care processes for post-RARC care and supported clinical decisions based on the patient health condition. This quality improvement project helped improve communication and provided a standardized method for documenting completion of the 2017 ERAS pathway components. Moreover, clinical practice variability has decreased between healthcare providers and decision making for IDT members was facilitated by consistent and improved communication. The need to write daily orders was not necessary and the patients progressed along the pre-determined trajectory of the 2017 ERAS pathway. Patients were informed and empowered by providing them with a post-RARC daily plan of care and activities to accomplish until discharge (see Appendix H).

During the implementation and post-intervention period, there was a reduction of 30-day RA rates, LOS, complications, increase in patient satisfaction and return of bowel activity at a shorter time post-RARC. The results showed a decrease in RA values from six (30%) to one (5%) in the post-intervention period. In addition, there was a decrease in

the average LOS from 11.5 days to 5.5 days in the post-intervention period. These findings were consistent with the Tyson & Chang (2016) and Azhar et al. (2016) studies which demonstrated a 39% complication rate in the ERAS compared to 51% for standard care. Moreover, the studies showed a 15% RA rate in 2017 ERAS compared to 52% for standard care. There was a one-day return of bowel function for the 2017 ERAS compared to a longer duration of bowel function return in standard care post-RARC.

There was a decrease in the incidence of DVT from 3(15%) to zero percent in the post-intervention period. The absence of the development of DVT from 85% to 100% post-RARC was evident. These improvements were consistent with the Pariser et al. (2015) study, which demonstrated that Low Molecular Weight Heparin (LMWH) or Enoxaparin regimen led to a 12% decrease in VTE cases. The clinician's decision to use Low-Density Heparin (LDH) or LMWH was based on the patient's renal function (Nomura et al., 2013). There were revisions made in the 2017 ERAS pathway operationalized in the form of order sets. One significant revision made was the inclusion of serum creatinine clearance parameters. The revised 2017 ERAS pathway was comprised of VTE prophylaxis recommendations and included: 1) heparin 5,000 units subcutaneously every eight hours after surgery if creatinine clearance is less than 15 ml per minute, 2) Enoxaparin 40mg subcutaneously if creatinine clearance is greater than 30 ml per hour, and 3) Enoxaparin 30mg subcutaneously if creatinine clearance is less than 30ml per minute (Cerantola et al., 2013; Nomura et al., 2013).

There was a decreased incidence of post-operative ileus, an indicator of faster return of bowel function. This finding was evident in the decrease from 10(50%) during the pre-intervention period to 2(10%) in the post-intervention period. These findings were

congruent with the Lee et al. (2014) and Choi et al. (2011) studies. These studies demonstrated that the use of Alvimopan 12mg divided into 15 doses and gum chewing every hour for seven days post- RARC may accelerate return of bowel function, shorten LOS, and a possible decrease in hospital costs. Moreover, the use of non-opioid analgesics such as IV acetaminophen or NSAIDS as baseline post-operative pain treatment facilitated early mobilization and return of bowel function based on the Cerantola et al. (2013) study.

Furthermore, adherence to early oral feeding within 24 hours showed decreased time to first bowel movement, decreased LOS without increasing complication rates and gastrointestinal function stimulation as discussed in the Collins et al. (2016) study. Improvement in the completion of early oral feeding within 24 hours was evident during the post-intervention period. The completion of early oral feeding increased from 13(65%) during the pre-intervention period to 19(95%) in the post-intervention period. The Cerantola et al. (2013) study discussed the importance of early oral feeding for maintenance of homeostasis. Normal diet should be implemented and re-established as early as possible since prolonged fasting after RARC was not evidence supported (Cerantola et al., 2013). However, none of the studies in the Cerantola et al. (2013) study explored a direct association of early oral feeding with LOS, RA rate and a decrease in post-operative ileus.

The 2017 ERAS component on post-analgesia completion demonstrated an increase from 7(35%) to 18(90%) in the post-intervention period. This component entails optimization of post-operative pain management and enhancement of recovery without negative impact on post-operative ileus and post-operative nausea and vomiting (Collins

et al, 2016). The pain management concept of starting intravenous IV acetaminophen or ibuprofen (Caldolor) demonstrated a decrease in the incidence of post-operative ileus and completion of early mobilization (Collins et al, 2016). The urology fellows, pharmacists, and nurses found that the 2017 ERAS with CPG standardized practice, and enhanced communication and documentation easy to use as found during informal interviews.

There was a notable improvement in the completion of early mobilization component from 17(85%) to 19(95%) in the post-intervention period. Since pain was better managed and reduced, the patients were able to participate in early mobilization in POD zero to one. This finding was congruent with the Cerantola et al. (2013) and Collins et al. (2016) studies.

Project Limitations

This QI project has limitations that need to be addressed. Since, this was a pilot project, the length of the project was short and thus the findings and implications may not be sustained should the project be conducted over a longer period of time. The post-implementation was limited to four months which was not sufficient to measure practice changes. The element of bias was present. The project leader and research assistant recorded the data and were familiar with the goals of the project. The DNP author was also the project leader and was highly involved in the facilitation of the completion of the five components of the 2017 ERAS pathway. However, efforts were made to combat this bias by having outside experts examine the data. The outside experts mentioned the possibility of bias, and thus their involvement in the project helped to decrease this bias. The improvements in the completion of the five 2017 ERAS pathway components were attributed to having the project leader facilitate the practice change during the

implementation phase. Moreover, the sample size was small and could have limited the scope of the implications found for practice and outcomes.

Implications

There were several factors that enabled the improvements to standardization in communication and documentation after the revision and CPG integration into the 2017 ERAS pathway. First, the in-service sessions held on a bi-weekly basis with the nurses and other IDT members generated enthusiasm and motivation to implement the project. During this period, a culture of team work and accountability to achieve the project's goals were evident. Second, IDT members felt that the 2017 ERAS and CPG helped them understand the importance of completing the ERAS components. Using the CPGs in their decision making helped to improve their workflow in post-RARC care. Third, a unit performance report was made available to the nurses and IDT members involved in post-RARC care. The report was based on 20 random chart reviews or audits and showed improvement in the project's outcome measured.

There were barriers encountered during the four-month intervention period. The culture of inefficiency among IDT members and nurses were not evaluated since the 2014 ERAS pathway was initially implemented. There were several new nurses who replaced the seasoned nurses since 2014 when the ERAS pathway was initially implemented. Follow-up in-service sessions for newly hired nurses since the implementation of the 2014 ERAS pathway did not take place. The sharing of transparent data among IDT members and nurses galvanized a culture of accountability.

After implementation of the 2017 ERAS pathway, workflow improved as evidenced by standardization of documentation and communication process. The revised

2017 ERAS pathway included the current CPGs integrated into policy and procedures and updated order sets. The revised 2017 ERAS pathway should undergo annual evaluation and revision to ensure that the practice changes are current. Quarterly chart audits should be conducted to enable IDT members to be accountable and engaged when taking care of post-RARC patients. The revised 2017 ERAS pathway of post- RARC will continue to evolve and require continuous incorporation of the essential components of quality improvement of post-RARC care.

Conclusion

Enhanced Recovery after Surgery are multi-modal care pathways that optimize recovery after RARC (Azhar et al., 2016). The DNP clinicians are the leaders in promoting patient care processes and outcomes through development and implementation of current CPGs. This EBP quality improvement project demonstrated standardized communication for documenting ERAS component completion. This DNP project aimed to revise the 2014 ERAS pathway to integrate EBP guidelines and evaluate its effect on documentation and communication. The goals were accomplished in four phases: 1) planning (input), 2) development (output), 3) implementation and adoption (outcome), and 4) sustainability (long- term outcomes). The ERAS pathway will continue to evolve with advancement in pharmacology, technology, and medicine. Thus, standardized reporting remains crucial in facilitating QI assessment (Collins et al., 2016).

One of the limitations of the 2014 ERAS pathway was inconsistent documentation of its implementation. Some IDT members of the urology team found it difficult to follow the 2014 ERAS pathway due to the lack of CPG. When the CPG were included in the 2017 ERAS pathway, post-RARC care and improvement of outcomes

were optimized, and evident in the post-intervention period. The LOS, RA rates, incidence of DVT and post-operative ileus decreased. Moreover, there was an increase in patient satisfaction with regards to their post-RARC care. The purpose and aims of this DNP project were accomplished in terms of being able to pilot and revise the 2017 ERAS pathway with CPG. Improvement in documentation and communication related to completion of the ERAS pathway was evident. This project was able to develop and rejuvenate a culture of improvement and compliance among IDT members involved in the care of post-RARC patients. The enthusiasm and commitment of the IDT members galvanized the sustainability of this quality improvement project.

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APPENDIX A**PHYSICIAN ORDERS****2014 Cystectomy Post-Operative Orders**

****Please also see orders for Post-Op days 1-5****

1. Admit to Telemetry
2. DX: SIP cystectomy and
3. Attending:
4. Allergies
5. Condition

6. Vital Signs and I and O's: per routine
 - Notify MD If:
 - a. Temperature greater than 38.3°C
 - b. BP greater than 190/ 100 or less than 90/60
 - c. HR greater than 120 or less than 60 beats per minute
 - d. Respiration greater than 26 or less than 8 breaths per minute
 - e. Urine output less than 30 ml per hour
7. **OOB to chair tonight**
8. NPO except sips for meds if indicated.
9. Pneumatic compression devices to legs when in bed
10. Inspiratory Spirometer 10X every hour while awake

11. Jackson Pratt/Blake to bulb suction
 12. Foley or SP tube to gravity drainage. Aspirate catheter then Irrigate catheter with 60 ml 0.9% NACL every 4 hours until clear and as needed to keep urine clear of clot or mucous.
 13. Bilateral ureteral stents to gravity drainage.
 14. BMP and H&H after surgery
 15. Nasal swab for MRSA

MD Printed Name, _____Signature_____Title__, Date__Time. __ RN Noted, Printed

Name **Signature** Title Date **Time**

PHYSICIAN ORDERS**2014 Cystectomy Post-Operative Orders**

Medications:

1. IV hydration: D5NS at 125 ml/hr. Decrease rate to 75 ml/hour when tolerating regular diet.
2. **Entereg 12 mg PO BID x 5 days** (exclude patients who have taken therapeutic doses of opioids,

MS contin 30mg BID, 2: 7 consecutive days) (Does not require a non-formulary approval for this

indication)

3. Caldolor 800 mg IV q 6 hours pm mild to moderate pain for a maximum of 4 doses total (includes intra-op doses, hold for allergy to aspirin or other NSAIDs, GFR ≥ 30 or Creatinine $2: 1.3$) (Use of 4 doses has been permitted by P&T for this indication only)
4. Acetaminophen (Tylenol) 650 mg PO q 6 hours' pm temperature greater than 38.3°C (do not to exceed 3 grams / 24 hours)
5. Acetaminophen (Tylenol) 650 mg PO q 6 hours pm mild to moderate pain not relieved by Caldolor (do not exceed 3 grams/24 hours)
6. Ofirmev (IV acetaminophen) pm mild to moderate pain: If > 50 kg give 1 g IV q 8 hours pm maximum 3 g/d, if < 50 kg give 15mg/kg q 8 hours pm maximum 75mg/kg/day (only if Caldolor is contraindicated-requires non-formulary drug request)
7. PCA: For severe pain not relieved by Cal dolor and Acetaminophen: Please complete the PCA order set. The following regimen is preferred:
 - a. Dilaudid bolus 0.1 mg q 10 minutes pm, may increase by 0.1 mg q 6 hours up to a maximum of 0.3 mg q 10 minutes. RN bolus of 0.5 mg q 120 minutes pm pain.
 8. Protonix 40 mg IV q day X 2 days, then Famotidine 20 mg IV Q 12 hours
 9. Ondansetron (Zofran) 4 mg IV q 6 hours' pm nausea/vomiting
 10. Ambien 5 mg po qhs pm insomnia (See insomnia orders)
 11. Lovenox per VTE prophylaxis protocol to initiation on POD 1 (first dose to be administered 2 hours' pre-op)
12. Electrolyte replacement:
 - a. If potassium 3.1-3.5: administer potassium chloride ER cap 40 mEq PO once. If unable to tolerate oral, administer potassium chloride 40 mEq IVPB over 4 hours once.
 - b. If potassium < 3.1 : administer potassium Chloride 80 mEq IVPB over 8 hours once.
 - c. Notify MD pm K^{+} less than or equal to 3.0.
 - d. If magnesium < 1.6 : administer magnesium sulfate 2 g IVPB over 2 hours once.

POST-OP CYSTECTOMY Day 1:

1. Chewing gum at least 1 X per hour and ad lib while awake, otherwise NPO
2. Ambulate with Assistance TID
3. CBC and BMP in am, if K+ less than 3.5 add serum Mg level onto labs and notify MD
4. H&H at noon-if Hgb less than 28 hold Lovenox and notify MD
5. Begin Patient Family teaching re: leg bag and instructions for irrigation of pouch, suprapubic tube/foley with NS
6. Begin Patient teaching for ileal conduit appliance care
7. Begin Patient teaching for Lovenox administration
8. Change xeroform gauze to stoma daily

POST-OP CYSTECTOMY day 2:

- I. Diet: Clear liquids, 8 ounces per 8 hours
2. Care Coordinator to instruct patient on Diet needs (2 liters/day and liquid calories), and Continue catheter care education –
3. Nutrition consult
4. CM to confirm DC plan in place

POST-OP CYSTECTOMY day 3:

1. Diet: Unrestricted clear liquids
2. CBC, BMP in am
3. Ibuprofen 600 mg po q 6 hours' pm moderate pain (hold for allergy to aspirin or other NSAIDs, GFR: 30 or Creatinine ~ 1.3)
4. Dilaudid 1 mg PO Q3 hours pm moderate pain not relieved with Ibuprofen
5. Dilaudid 2 mg PO q 3 hours' pm severe pain
6. Dilaudid 0.25 mg IV q 1 hour pm severe pain not relieved with oral Dilaudid –
7. Call pain consult pm pain uncontrolled off PCA, Goal to minimize narcotic use, minimize ileus, and get patient home on oral medications with pain controlled
8. Care coordinator to Instruct on use of leg bag, ostomy bag, and irrigations
9. Care coordinator to do Medication reconciliation with home medications
10. CM to verify all DC meds and supplies available
11. CM to review side effects for home medications and that patient is tolerating lovenox and oral Dilaudid. If not, please page MD to change Medication regimen –
12. DC PCA
13. Care Coordinator to administer Support Screen

2014 Cystectomy Post-Operative Orders**POST-OP CYSTECTOMY day 4:**

1. Diet: Regular
2. DuIcolax 10 mg PR BID
3. Care coordinator to confirm understanding of catheter irrigation, leg and night time bags, management of JP drain if indicated, ileal conduit or stoma appliance care, Pain management, signs and symptoms requiring immediate medical attention, need for 2 liters of fluid/day
4. Care coordinator to confirm F/U appt for 3 and 7 days' post DC

POST-OP CYSTECTOMY day 5:

1. CBC, BMP
2. Milk of magnesia 30 ml po BID, hold for loose stool
3. DC IV and insert new IV and hep- lock
4. DC home
5. Care coordinator to do Medication reconciliation with home meds

APPENDIX B

REVISED 2017 CYSTECTOMY POST-OPERATIVE ORDERS

Cystectomy with Creation of Urinary Diversion Post Operative [65 orders of 202 are selected]

Order Opiemv (acetaminophen IV) outside of this orderset ONLY if Ibuprofen IV (Caldolor) is contraindicated. A non-formulary drug request is required to order Opiemv. Dosing Recommendations for Opiemv: If wt GREATER THAN 50 kg give 1 gram IV every 8 hrs for 2 day mg/day. After 2 days, order oral Acetaminophen 1000 mg every 8 hours daily for 3 days or for wt LESS THAN 50 kg, 15 mg/kg every 8 hours for 3 days. Maximum of 3000 mg for any weight.

Pain Management - IV

Order	Dose	Unit	Route	Frequency	PRN	PRN Reason	Therapy Sequence	Start Priority	Start Date	Stop After	Special Instructions	Withhold Dose If
[-] Ibuprofen - 1 item(s)												
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ibuprofen IV	800	mg	IntraVenous	every 6 hours	<input type="checkbox"/>			Routine	Nov-28-2017	17 Doses	Start 8 hours AFTER...	GFR LESS than or equal...
[-] Dilaudid - 2 item(s)												
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HYDROMORPHONE inj	0.1	mg	IntraVenous Push	every hour	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	moderate pain (pain scale...		Routine	Nov-28-2017		After POST-OP DAY...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HYDROMORPHONE inj	0.25	mg	IntraVenous Push	every hour	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	severe pain (pain scale 7-...		Routine	Nov-28-2017		After POST-OP DAY...	

Recommend Dosing: HYDROMORPHONE Bolus 0.1 mg every 10 minutes as needed. May increase by 0.1 mg every 60 minutes up to a Maximum of 0.3 mg every 10 minutes. Nurse bolus of 0.5 mg every 120 minutes as needed for pain.

Other Pain Management

Patient Controlled Analgesia Consult - Supportive Care

Cystectomy with Creation of Urinary Diversion Post Operative [65 orders of 202 are selected]

Provider to Nurse Communication

Order	Start Date	Instructions
[-] Provider to Care Coordinator - 2 item(s)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Provider to Nurse Communication	Nov-29-2017	POST-OP DAY 1: Care Coordinator to confirm discharge plan in place
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Provider to Nurse Communication	Dec-03-2017	POST-OP DAY 5: Care Coordinator: Discharge teaching for plan of care at home
[-] Provider to Nurse - 4 item(s)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Provider to Nurse Communication	Nov-29-2017	POST-OP DAY 1-3: Encourage patient to chew gum at least 1 time per hour and AD LIB while awake.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Provider to Nurse Communication	Nov-30-2017	POST-OP DAY 2: Ensure provider has discontinued PCA.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Provider to Nurse Communication	Dec-03-2017	PRIOR TO DISCHARGE: Please ensure provider has completed medication reconciliation for Post-operative day 5. (A) Enoxaparin 40mg Subcutaneous daily for 25...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Provider to Nurse Communication	Dec-03-2017	PRIOR TO DISCHARGE: Ensure provider has ordered Urine Culture and Sensitivity for second post-discharge visit (7-10 post-discharge)

Referrals - POD 1

Physical Therapy - Evaluate and Treat
 Occupational Therapy - Evaluate and Treat

Consults/Referrals

Case Management - Discharge Planning
 Discharge Planning Evaluation

Cystectomy with Creation of Urinary Diversion Post Operative [65 orders of 202 are selected]

Diet

Order	Patient CAN HAVE the following	Carbohydrate Control	Start Priority	Start Date	Special Instructions
[-] Diet - IMMEDIATE POST-OP - 1 item(s)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NPO	Can Have Sips; Can Take Medication		Now	Nov-29-2017	
[-] Diet - POST OP DAY 1 - 1 item(s)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clear Liquid Diet			Routine	Nov-29-2017	Restricted - 8 ounces per 8 hours. Oikos Yogurt 3.
[-] Diet - POST OP DAY 2 - 1 item(s)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clear Liquid Diet			Routine	Nov-30-2017	No Restrictions. Oikos Yogurt 3 times a day with each.
[-] Diet - POST OP DAY 3 - 1 item(s)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Regular Diet			Routine	Dec-01-2017	Oikos Yogurt 3 times a day with each meal for 1.
[-] Diet - Other - 2 item(s)					
<input type="checkbox"/> Full Liquid Diet			Routine	T	Oikos Yogurt 3 times a day with each meal for 1 month.
<input type="checkbox"/> Advance Diet as Tolerated					

Nutrition Consult - POST OP DAY 2

 Consult - Clinical Dietitian

Order	Dose	Unit	Route	Frequency	Start Priority	Start Date	Special Instructions
[-] If CrCl is > or = 30 ml/min - 1 item(s)							
<input type="checkbox"/> enoxaparin inj	40	mg	SubCutaneous	every 24 hours	Routine	T	
[-] CrCl 11 to 29 ml/min - 1 item(s)							
<input type="checkbox"/> enoxaparin inj	30	mg	SubCutaneous	every 24 hours	Routine	T	
[-] If CrCl is < or = 10 ml/min - 1 item(s)							
<input type="checkbox"/> heparin 5,000 Unit(s) per 0.5 mL inj	5,000	Unit(s)	SubCutaneous	every 8 hours	Routine	T	
[-] Heparin Ind. Thrombocytopenia - 1 item(s)							
<input type="checkbox"/> fondaparinux inj	2.5	mg	SubCutaneous	every 24 hours	Routine	T	Do not use in patients with CrCl LESS THAN 30 mL/min OR in Neurosurgery Patients.

Order	Instructions
[-] Provider to Nurse - 1 item(s)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Provider to Nurse Communication	Anticoagulation needs to be administered within 24 hours POST end of surgery unless otherwise indicated.

Neobladder				
Order	Specify Teaching Topic	Frequency	Start Date	Special Instructions
[-] Urinary Catheter - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Urinary Catheter Indwelling, To Gravity		T	Foley Catheter
[-] Irrigate Urinary Catheter - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Urinary Catheter, Irrigate	every 4 hours	T	Aspirate prior to irrigations. Irrigate until clear...
[-] Post-Op Day 2 - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Education, Other	POST-OP DAY 2: Patient and caregiver to observe how nurse performs irrigation.	T+2	
[-] Post-Op Day 3 - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Education, Other	POST-OP DAY 3: Begin teaching patient and caregiver irrigation instructions.	T+3	
[-] Post-Op Day 4-5 - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Education, Other	POST-OP DAY 4-5: Reinforce teaching patient and caregiver irrigation instructions.	T+4	

Indiana Pouch				
Order	Specify Teaching Topics	Frequency	Start Date	Special Instructions
[-] Surgical Incision Care - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Wound Dressing Change	once a day	T+1	
[-] Urinary Catheter - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Urinary Catheter Indwelling, To Gravity		T	Suprapubic Catheter
[-] Irrigate Urinary Catheter - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Urinary Catheter, Irrigate	every 4 hours	T	Aspirate prior to irrigations. Irrigate until clear...
[-] Post-Op Day 2 - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Education, Other	POST-OP DAY 2: Patient and caregiver to observe how nurse performs irrigation.	T+2	
[-] Post-Op Day 3 - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Education, Other	POST-OP DAY 3: Begin teaching patient and caregiver irrigation instructions.	T+3	
[-] Post-Op Day 4-5 - 1 item(s)				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Education, Other	POST-OP DAY 4-5: Reinforce teaching patient and caregiver irrigation instructions.	T+4	

Activity							
Order	Ambulate	Assistive Device if Applicable	Additional Parameter	Frequency	Start Date	Stop After	Special Instructions
[-] Activity - 4 item(s)							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Up in Chair		with meals		Nov-28-2017		First evening post-op
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ambulate		with assistance	3 times a day	T+1		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Activity - Per Mobility Protocol				Nov-28-2017		Notify MD if patient is exempt from protocol.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Activity - No Restrictions				T		
[-] Other Activity - 1 item(s)							
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other Activity Orders						

APPENDIX C

ADHERENCE TO ERAS POST-OP COMPONENTS AUDIT (AUGUST – NOVEMBER 2016)

August 1 – 30, 2016

Patient ID	A	B	C	D	E
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
9					
10					
11					
12					
13					
14					
15					
16					
17					
18					
19					
20					

Note: A = Early mobilization POD 1

B = DVT prophylaxis POD 2

C = Post-op pain management; PCA dcd POD 2;

D = Early oral feeding w/in 24 hours & nutrition consult POD 2

**E = Prevention of post-op ileus (gum chewing every hour while awake x 7 days
+ Alvimopan 12mg = 15 doses max)**

ERAS Component Completion audit: 1 = Yes, completed; 0 = No, not completed

APPENDIX D

CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINES FOR POST-OPERATIVE CARE AFTER RADICAL CYSTECTOMY FOR BLADDER CANCER: ENHANCED RECOVERY AFTER SURGERY (ERAS)

The following ERAS post-radical cystectomy clinical practice guidelines were developed to optimize patient outcomes and standardize documentation and communication. These recommendations were founded on current evidence obtained from extensive review of literature and expert opinion.

Early Mobilization

Several studies have shown that there are similar results with an overall increase in functional capacity, quality of life improvement, patient outcome improvement, and reduction of post-operative morbidity when early mobilization is implemented (Jensen et al., 2016; Jones et al., 2010; Porserud et al., 2014). Cerantola et al (2013), made recommendations to encourage early ambulation of post –RC patients at least two hours out of bed on post-operative day (POD) zero and six hours out of bed on POD one.

The recommendation is strong based on the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) system. Moreover, the consensus view among the European Association of Urology (EAU) scientific working group, which was comprised of experts from high volume robotic, assisted radical cystectomy (RARC) hospitals in Europe, reached a 100 percent consensus regarding early ambulation. This recommendation also aids in the reduction of post-operative pain (Collins et al., 2016).

DVT Prophylaxis

The VTE Prophylaxis recommendations are comprise of 1) Heparin 5,000 units subcutaneously every eight hours to begin after surgery, 2) Enoxaparin 40mg subcutaneously daily if creatinine clearance is over 30 ml/min or 30 mg if the creatinine clearance is less than 30 ml/minute, 3) pneumatic compression device if high risk for bleeding. (Forrest et al., 2009; Geerts et al., 2008; Nomura et al., 2013).

Prevention of Post-Operative Ileus

The recommendation formulated from current evidence recommended gum chewing every hour from POD one to seven in combination with the use of Alvimopan 12mg to facilitate earlier return of bowel function, shorten LOS, and reduce hospital costs (Cerantola et al., 2013; Collins et al., 2016). The evidence level is moderate, and the recommendation grade is strong. The study showed robust evidence that chewing gum stimulates bowel motility after RC and urinary diversion. Studies have shown that gum chewing enhanced and promoted intestinal functioning and faster return to bowel function post-RC. The evidence exhibited that chewing gum was safe and could be used to reduce incidence of post-operative ileus (Choi et al., 2011).

Post-Operative Analgesia

The EAU robotic section scientific working group reached a 100% consensus and recommended standardized poly-pharmacologic opioid sparing analgesia. Baseline treatment includes intravenous (IV) acetaminophen if patient is unable to tolerate oral intake. It was also recommended to avoid epidural analgesia to promote early

mobilization (Collins et al., 2016). The evidence level is high, and the recommendation grade is strong under the GRADE system.

Early Oral Diet

The recommendation by Collins et al (2016) is to start daily nutritional supplements along with a nutritional goal of 900 kcal per day from POD two to four, 1500 kcal per day from POD four and onwards, with fluid and electrolytes at 30 ml/kg daily. The strength of the recommendation is strong, and the evidence level is moderate according to the GRADE system (Collins et al., 2016).

The five components are DVT prophylaxis, prevention of post-operative ileus, early mobilization, early oral feeding, and post-operative pain management. These components were reviewed for their significance in improving health outcomes after RARC. Each component was examined for its strength of research evidence and influence to affect patient care using the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) system. This system classifies each ERAS component as high, moderate, low, or very low based upon the quality of the research available for review. A high rating indicates that additional research will not change the confidence in the outcome of the benefit of the ERAS component. A moderate rating means additional research may change the confidence in the outcome of the benefit of the ERAS component. A low rating would indicate that additional research would impact the confidence in the outcome to have the desirable intended effects. A very low rating indicates that additional research would highly influence the confidence in the benefit of the ERAS component and warrant removal of it from the pathway.

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APPENDIX E

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD (IRB) ACTION NOTICE

TO: Cecilio Cay, MS, RN, NP, Principal Investigator
 City of Hope - Nursing Support-Med/Surg

FROM: Adam Pucci, CIP, IRB Operations Manager *Adam Pucci*
 Office of Human Research Subjects Protection

DATE: June 19, 2017

STUDY TITLE: Updating the Enhanced Recovery After Surgery Pathway: A Quality Improvement Project

IRB#/REF#: 17188 / 142536

SUBMISSION: SUBMISSION EVALUATION

IRB ACTION DATE: 06/19/2017

IRB ACTION:

The information provided for the above submission was evaluated and determined to not involve human subjects research (45 CFR 46.102 (d)(f)). Therefore, it does not need to be approved nor does it need to undergo continuing review by the Institutional Review Board (IRB).

The above determination is based on the understanding that information gathered during the project is to be utilized internally for quality improvement purposes. Should the circumstances of the project change such that there is intent to gather information or use any information previously gathered for research purposes, the IRB must be notified via an amendment or separate submission prior to implementation for a determination of whether IRB review is required.

NOTE: IF ANY CHANGES IN THE RESEARCH INVOLVING HUMAN SUBJECTS ARE PLANNED, A SEPARATE SUBMISSION UNDER A NEW IRB NUMBER MUST BE MADE ACCORDING TO REGULAR SUBMISSION REQUIREMENTS. NO CHANGES INVOLVING HUMAN SUBJECTS MAY BE INITIATED UNTIL REVIEW HAS BEEN OBTAINED.

If you have questions or concerns about this submission, please contact Keith Meinking/Suzanne Kelly.

APPENDIX F

RE: IRB documents for Cecilio Cay DNP student SF17-1 Darlene Finocchiaro and Cecilia Cay
Updating the Enhanced Recovery After Surgery Pathway: A Quality Improvement Project Inbox x

 IRB <irb@calstatela.edu>

10/16/17

to Darlene, me, Darlene, Cecilio, Jason, Sharon

Dr. Finocchiaro,

Based upon the information you have submitted to the IRB, your project (SF17-1 Darlene Finocchiaro and Cecilia Cay Updating the Enhanced Recovery After Surgery Pathway: A Quality Improvement Project) does not seem to meet the definition of research according to the federal regulations, 45 CFR 46, as it appears that it is not a systematic investigation, including research development, testing and evaluation, that is designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge. If this differs from your intent, further IRB review will be required.

Thanks,

Elia

From: Finocchiaro, Darlene Nelson

Sent: Friday, October 13, 2017 1:54 PM

To: Amaro-Hernandez, Elia <EAmaro@cslanet.calstatela.edu>

Subject: FW: IRB documents for Cecilio Cay DNP student

Importance: High

Elia

APPENDIX G

PRE-AND POST-TEST: IN-SERVICE SESSIONS

1. ERAS stands for Enhanced Recovery after Surgery.
True
False
2. Post- radical cystectomy patients need to be out of bed within six hours' post-op in order to reduce their risk of DVT and PE.
True
False
3. The administration of Lovenox 40 mg subcutaneously daily should be initiated on post-operative day 1 with serum creatinine clearance parameters t as part of the new clinical practice guideline.
True
False
4. Post -op pain management should start with an opioid pain medication instead of IV Acetaminophen or IV NSAIDS.
True
False
5. Gum Chewing should be started on post-op day 1 and given at a frequency of every hour only on the first -op day.
True
False
6. Pain management needs to be consulted if pain is not well controlled in order to prevent unnecessary hospital stay.
True
False
7. When PCA analgesia is administered, the ERAS pathway states that the PCA should be discontinued on post-op day 3 to reduce incidence of post-op ileus.
True
False
8. The Urology case manager should render the Support Screen on post-op day 3 to assess for possible depression and support if needed.
True
False
9. A nutrition consult should be initiated when the patient is still unable to tolerate oral intake and unable to pass flatus in 5 to 6 days to assess for possible parenteral nutrition.
True
False
10. The teaching for the management of the urinary diversion appliance is only the responsibility of the care coordinator.
True
False

APPENDIX H

Your Cystectomy Plan of Care

Listed below are activities you are expected to do as part of your plan of care. Always speak up if you do not understand something or if you are unsure of any instructions you may receive. Good communication is at the center of receiving excellent care at City of Hope

APPENDIX I

Table 1

Components of ERAS Post-RC Care: Prevention of Post-Operative Ileus

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To resolve whether chewing gum facilitates bowel function return in post radical cystectomy period. (Choi et al., 2011)	<p>Study design: Prospective RCT</p> <p>IDV: CG = ORC & RARC NGum chewing : IG = ORC & RARC Gum chewing group</p> <p>DV: Operative outcomes</p>	<p>Sample: 60 PT (ORC+RARC)</p> <p>ORC = 32 17 NGum; 15 Gum</p> <p>RARC = 28 13 NGum; 15 Gum</p> <p>CG (NGum): 17+13 = 30</p> <p>IG (Gum): 15 + 15 = 30</p> <p>AGE (Years) CG = 64.5 +/- 8.8 IG = 63.5 +/- 4.5</p> <p>Setting: Seoul, Korea</p>	<p>Operative Outcomes:</p> <p>: TTF (H)</p> <p>: TBM (H)</p> <p>: Narcotic use (%)</p> <p>: GI COMP = IC, PI (%)</p> <p>: HS (D)</p>	<p>Med time to flatus & BM ↓ in PTs in IG = 57.1 H vs 69.5 H vs PT in CG.</p> <p>TTF in CG = 60.3 H vs 48.8 H in IG ($p < .01$)</p> <p>TBM in CG = 84.6 H vs. 69 H in IG ($p < .01$)</p>	<p>No Diff in narcotic use, OP, & EBL</p> <p>HS = No diff b/w CG vs IG</p> <p>1st Flatus & TBM shorter 12.4 & 16.4 H in IG vs. CG.</p> <p>HS = No diff b/w CG vs IG</p>

Table 2

Components of ERAS: Prevention of Post-Operative Ileus

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To assess efficacy of Alvimopan to accelerate GI recovery after RC (Lee et al., 2014).	Study Design: RCT IV: LOS : Opioid use : Post-Op ileus Related morbidity : Cardiac events : GI recovery time DV: Alvimopan 15 mg : Placebo	Sample: N = 250 RC pts. IG: Alvimopan 12 mg (n = 143) CG: Placebo (n = 137) Setting: 21 high volume academic sites (> 50 cases a year) across the USA	Opioid consumption (%) Post-Op Ileus (%) LOS (days) GI recovery time (days) CV events (%)	Alvimopan cohort: Quicker GI recovery ($p < .0001$); 5.5 days vs. 6.9 days in placebo Shorter LOS ($p = .005$) Fewer episodes of POI related morbidity ($p < .001$) 8.4 % Alvimopan vs. 29.1% in placebo 8.4% Alvimopan vs 15.3% in placebo group in CV events($p = .09$).	Alvimopan provides significant early post-operative outcome improvement for pts. undergoing RC. It hastens GI recovery & shortens LOS vs placebo group. Limitations: GI recovery post-RC depends on intra-op fluid administration, bowel segment selection, lymphadenectomy extent, surgical technique & re-adaptation of peritoneum. Limited generalizability due to exclusion of epidural analgesia & inclusion of centers using open laparotomy

Table 3

Components of ERAS: Early Oral Feeding

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To study the impact of early feeding on recovery in randomized multi institutional protocol (Delbert et al., 2016)	<p>Study design: RCT between 2011-2014</p> <p>IV: Early feeding (ERAS) & Standard Care (SC)</p> <p>DV : Complications (VTE, infection, PONV) : Diet tolerance : LOS : RA : POI/Flatus</p>	<p>102 patients who had RC: 1, Early feeding group = 50 2. Standard /Normal feeding group = 52</p> <p>Setting: 2 large Hospitals in the USA</p>	<p>Complications (%)</p> <p>LOS(days)</p> <p>RA (%)</p> <p>Rates of ileus (%)</p> <p>POI/Flatus(days)</p> <p>Infection (%)</p>	<p>Primary outcomes: Complications (40 % in early feeding/ERAS vs 82%, (SC), $p = .86$)</p> <p>Non-Significant</p> <p>Secondary outcomes: 1.Rates of ileus: 27% vs 41%</p> <p>2. Time to full diet tolerance = same 5.7 vs 6.7 days</p> <p>3. LOS = not different, 6.7 vs. 9.7 days</p> <p>4. RA rate similar, 22 % vs 23 %</p>	The RCT showed that early oral feeding is well tolerated and has neither have a + or (-) impact in outcomes.

Table 4

Components of ERAS: Early Enteral Feeding within 24 hours Post-Op

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To assess early enteral nutrition within 24 hours, post-gastrointestinal surgery compared to traditional care (Lewis et al., 2009).	<p>Study design: Systematic review & Meta-analysis</p> <p>IDV: early enteral feeding w/in 24 hrs. post-op or treatment grp (TG) : Late initiation of feeding post-op or control group(TG)</p> <p>DV: Wound infection, pneumonia, anastomotic leak/dehiscence, mortality, LOS</p>	<p>Sample: 13 studies = 1,173 total</p> <p>Setting: UK & Denmark,</p>	<p>LOS = days</p> <p>Wound infection (%)</p> <p>Pneumonia = (%)</p> <p>Anastomotic leak/dehiscence (%)</p> <p>Mortality (%)</p>	<p>↓LOS reported in 12 out of 13 studies: Mean LOS early feeding grp (IG) = 6.2-19 days vs. 6.8 -16 days in CG. Thus, ↓LOS for IG ($p = .09$).</p> <p>↓Mortality = pooled analysis favored the IG based on Forest plot ($p < .03$)</p> <p>Absolute risks % in TG: ↓wound infection = 0-14 % vs 33% in CG; ↓anastomotic dehiscence = 0-8% vs. 0-40% in CG; pneumonia = 0-6% vs. 0-7% in CG; mortality = 0-6.7% vs. 0-19% in CG</p>	<p>This SR has shown that keeping pts nothing by mouth within 24 hrs post-op has no benefit. Early enteral feeding may ↓mortality, ↓infectious complications, & LOS.</p> <p>Limitations: detection of heterogeneity b/w trials limited by small # of pts trials & inadequate reporting of randomization methods, outcome assessment & blinding.</p> <p>There was publication bias to the included trials or for any of reported outcomes.</p>

Table 5

Components of ERAS: Post-Radical Cystectomy Deep Vein Thrombosis Prophylaxis

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
Reviewed published data for the safety and efficacy of extended thrombo-prophylaxis (6-14 days) in high risk pts for VTE, cost effectiveness, & in-patient to out- patient setting transition (Huo & Muntz, 2009)	<p>Study Design: Systematic Review:</p> <p>IV: -Extended duration of thrombo-prophylaxis w/ LMWH -Standard duration w/ LMWH</p> <p>DV: symptomatic DVT/PE : cost per event : DVT / PE events</p>	<p>Prospective randomized Enoxaparin & Cancer II (ENOXACAN II) pts for abdominal & pelvic cancer surgery = 343 surgical pts. Got LMWH or Enoxaparin x 6-10 days followed by Enoxaparin or placebo x 21 more days.</p> <p>IC: prospective randomized design + control group</p> <p>EC: Case series and retrospective analysis</p> <p>Setting: Houston and Dallas Texas</p>	<p>Extended duration of thrombo-prophylaxis (EDT) (25-35 days)</p> <p>Standard duration (SDT); (6-11 days)</p> <p>Symptomatic DVT/PE (%)</p> <p>Cost per event (\$)</p> <p># of DVT/PE events</p>	<p>ENOXACAN II RCT</p> <p>Incidence of symptomatic & asymptomatic VTE = 4.8% (8/165) in Enoxaparin grp vs 12% (20/167) in placebo grp. Thus, a 60 % ↓ for Enoxaparin ($p = .02$)</p> <p>Comb. incidence of VTE in 3 months: LMWH = 5.5%(9/165) placebo = 13.8%(23/167) = ↓ VTE w/ LMWH ($p = .01$) = ↓ proximal DVT/PE in double blind & 3-month LMWH extended duration regimens.</p> <p>4-5-week duration of VTE prophylaxis = prevent 30 clinical DVT & 18 PE events per 1,000 pts + 2,000 \$ savings per event.</p>	<p>High risk surgical pts benefit from extended-duration thrombo-prophylaxis to ↓ risk of late VTE. LMWH is effective and has low rate of bleeding & is cost effective.</p> <p>Limitations: This is not a SR or MA of all available data. Studies limited to reported LMWH & extended DVT prophylactic use Safety review based mainly on major relevant adverse events. Data on clinical trials may not reflect actual clinical practice,</p>

Table 6

Components of ERAS: Post- Radical Cystectomy Deep Vein Thrombosis Prophylaxis

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To determine if UFH & LMWH reduces in-hospital VTE in unselected medically ill pts. ((Kanaan et al., 2007)	<p>Study design: Meta-analysis</p> <p>IV: LMWH : UFH : Fondaparinux : Placebo</p> <p>DV : DVT : PE</p>	<p>Sample: 14 studies (881 total) Included studies = 9 Excluded studies = 5</p> <p>IC: RCT</p> <p>EC: pts who failed to have minimum JADAD score of 3 due to lack of randomization</p>	DVT/PE/VTE (events on day 7 through 21)	<p>↓DVT/PE/VTE events w/ use of LMWH/fondaparinux vs placebo or UFH w/ Absolute Risk Reduction (ARR) of 1.36% and Number Needed to Treat (NTT) of 74. ($p < .001$)</p> <p>No difference in VTE-related deaths b/w LMWH/fondaparinux or placebo ($p = .47$)</p> <p>No difference in DVT incidence when comparing LMWH/fondaparinux vs UFH alone ($p = .75$) suggesting LMWH & UFH are similar in DVT event reduction in medically ill pts.</p>	<p>↓rates of VTE in medically ill pts when given pharmacologic thromboembolic prophylaxis w/ LMWH/UFH & effective in reduction of DVT but did not enhance PE protection. Important to pts & institution specific factors VTE prophylaxis selection (renal function, heparin induced thrombocytopenia, risks, & formulary restrictions.</p> <p>Limitations: Not all studies used same VTE criteria for dx & definition of bleeding. Not ideal to group LMWH in 1 drug class Only English language studies included in the meta-analysis.</p>

Table 7

Components of ERAS: Pre-habilitation and Early Mobilization Post-Radical Cystectomy

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To explore feasibility, compliance, & efficacy of short term pre-habilitation programs to PTs w/ IBC awaiting RC (Jensen, Lautsen, Jensen, Borre, & Petersen, 2016)	<p>Study Design: Secondary data on a prospective RCT</p> <p>IV: demographics : clinical attributes</p> <p>DV: adherence to & efficacy of pre-op exercise</p>	<p>Sample: 107 patients</p> <p>IG = 50 CG = 57</p> <p>Setting: Denmark</p>	<p>IDVs: Gender(M/F) Co-morbidity (Charlston;<2, = ,>2) Age (years)</p> <p>DV: Adherence, Self-report</p>	<p>Intervention: M: 39; F: 11 Mean age = 69</p> <p>Standard: M: 40; W: 17 Mean age = 71</p> <p>PT reported: 66% adhered > 75% with pre-habilitation program.</p> <p>MRP: improvement of 0.35 W/kg in MP at time of SX vs. baseline ($p < .002$).</p>	<p>PT waiting for RC – MRP is feasible & effective</p> <p>Pre-op PT assessment, pre-habilitation is relevant, improves physical capacity, & promotes early recovery & early ambulation.</p> <p>PHI should be explored as adjuvant to improve PT outcome & ↓ post-op morbidity.</p>

Table 8

Components of ERAS: Early Mobilization Post-Radical Cystectomy

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To assess the feasibility of exercise training program in post-radical cystectomy pts (Porserud et al., 2014)	<p>Study Design: Single-blind pilot RCT</p> <p>IV: Intervention group = 6-minute walk test, grp exercise training x 12-weeks : Control group = standardized information at discharge : Training Period (T1, T2, T3)</p> <p>DV: walking distance : functional capacity (walking) : SF 36 role physical domain</p>	<p>Sample: 18 pts out of 89 eligible pts ,64-78 years of age Total = 122</p> <p>Setting: University Hospital in Sweden</p>	<p>Walking distance (meters)</p> <p>Functional capacity (6-minute walk test = hours per week)</p> <p>14 weeks' post-op (hours per week)</p> <p>1-year post surgery (hours per week)</p> <p>T1 = baseline T2 = w/in 14 weeks' post-op T3 = 1yr post-op</p> <p>SF-36 scoring = Quality of life</p>	<p>Total 18 pts: IG = 9 (4 dropped); CG = 9 (1 dropped) = 13 pts completed T1&T2. IG = 5 pts ↑walking distance > CG = 8 pts: 109 meters vs. 62 meters respectively ($p = .013$)</p> <p>Role physical domain SF- 36 > CG($p = .031$)</p> <p>Total 10 pts IG = 4 + CG = 6 completed T1, T2, T3& evaluated 1yr post-op: IG ↑walking distance by 20 meters vs. CG ↓ distance by -15.5 meters ($p = .010$)</p> <p>100 meter ↑in distance in IG; 75 meters ↑in distance in CG.</p>	<p>12-week group exercise training regimens were not feasible for most cystectomy pts. Functional capacity ↑in the short and long term for the IG vs. CG pts.</p>

Table 9

Components of ERAS: Prevention of Post-Operative Nausea and Vomiting

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To correlate the effects of Dexamethasone and Ondansetron in prevention of post-op nausea & vomiting in pts scheduled for laparoscopic surgery (Wang et al., 2015)	<p>Study Design: Meta-analysis of RCTs</p> <p>IV Types of post-op anti-emetic used: - Dexamethasone - Ondansetron</p> <p>DV: PONV -Early post-op stage -w/in 24 hrs. of lap surgery -Late post-op stage</p>	<p>7 RCTs using Fixed Effects Model: = 608 pts total</p> <p>Setting: China</p>	<p>Primary outcome: Early post-op stage 0-6 hrs.</p> <p>Secondary outcomes: -w/in 24 hrs. of lap surgery -Late post-op stage 6-24 hrs.</p>	<p>Early post-op period: Ondansetron better in preventing PONV vs. Dexamethasone ($p = .03$).</p> <p>Late post-op period: Dexamethasone better in preventing PONV ($p = .03$).</p> <p>Secondary outcomes: No significant difference in anti-emetic used w/in 24 hrs. Post-op ($p = .45$). No heterogeneity ($p = .88$)</p> <p>No publication bias, ($p = .537$)</p>	<p>Dexamethasone was as effective & safe as Ondansetron in preventing PONV</p> <p>Limitations: No gold standard in PONV definition Based on studies published in English and bias a possibility. Sample size is small or moderate. Many studies not registered on clinical trial databases.</p>

Table 10

Components of ERAS: Prevention of Post-Op Nausea and Vomiting by Use of Combination Anti-Emetics

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To investigate if Ondansetron + Prochlorperazine when added to opioid PCA was more beneficial than Ondansetron alone in reducing PONV. Risk factors that ↑n/v were analyzed to assess if combination antiemetic use was more effective in pts at risk for PONV (Jellish et al., 2008).	<p>Study Design: RCT</p> <p>IDV: PCA + Saline</p> <p>Group C or control group (CG) = PCA+ saline</p> <p>IG: PCA + Ondansetron (Group O); PCA+ Ondansetron+ Prochlorperazine (Group OP)</p> <p>DV: Post-Operative Outcomes: Freq of PONV in 1st 24 hrs.; Freq of PONV in 24-48 hrs.; PCA Morphine use in 1st 24 hrs.; PCA Morphine in 24-48 hrs. PCA costs.</p>	<p>Sample = 150 pts undergoing abdominal surgery & using PCA analgesia</p> <p>Setting: University hospital at Maywood, Illinois</p>	<p>PONV 1st 24 hrs. (Frequency in %)</p> <p>PONV 24-48 hrs. (frequency in %)</p> <p>PCA Morphine use: 1st 24 hrs. = mg in 24-48 hrs. = mg</p> <p>PCA cost = \$ US</p>	<p>PONV in 1st 24 hrs. In hospital floor: Group C = ↑ freq PONV (10-12 %) Group OP = ↓ freq of nausea, 5-6 % vs. CG ($p = <.005$). -Group O = ↓ freq of vomiting, 4-5 %, ($p = <.005$)</p> <p>PONV up to 48 hrs: Recovery + Hospital floor: -Group C = ↑ freq, 10 % -Group OP = ↓ freq, ($p = .092$) -Group O = ↓ freq. vomiting ($p = .045$)</p> <p>Highest PCA cost in \$ US noted in Group OP vs. Group C.</p>	<p>There is benefit in using combination anti-emetics in Morphine PCA. But the effect does not last beyond 24 hrs. post-op. The combination anti-emetic is only effective in the 1st 24 hrs. post-op. Further studies to examine PCA use w/ other combination of anti-emetics.</p>

Table 11

Components of ERAS: Post-Operative Analgesia

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To assess the effects of IV Ibuprofen 400 & 800 mg iv every 6 hours in post-op pain management. (Southworth et al., 2009)	<p>Study Design: RCT</p> <p>IV: Ibuprofen 400 mg : Ibuprofen 800 mg : placebo</p> <p>DV: Primary outcome: Morphine use in 1st 24 hrs. post-op</p> <p>Secondary outcomes: Pain scores at rest Pain scores at movement</p>	<p>Sample: 406 pts -Women = 319 -Men = 87 -Mean age = 45 years -Weight = 83.8 kg</p> <p>Morphine PCA + Ibuprofen 400 mg = 134 pts.</p> <p>Morphine PCA + Ibuprofen 800 mg = 138 pts.</p> <p>Morphine PCA + Placebo = 134 pts.</p>	<p>Morphine usage in 1st 24 hrs. (%)</p> <p>Pain scores at rest using Visual Analog Scale (VAS)</p> <p>Pain scores at movement using VAS</p>	<p>Intention to Treat: ↓ Morphine usage with 1st 24 hrs. & received Ibuprofen 800 mg by 22% vs. placebo ($p = .030$)</p> <p>↓pain at rest ↓pain at movement (1-24; 6-24; 12-24 hrs.) vs. placebo</p> <p>↓in GI disorder experience in the 400 mg ($p = .05$) & 800 mg ($p = .09$) IV Ibuprofen groups</p>	<p>↓in morphine use, pain at rest & w/ movement in the Ibuprofen 800 mg vs. placebo.</p> <p>IV Ibuprofen not a/w adverse reactions</p>

Table 12

Components of ERAS: Post-Operative Analgesia Comparison in ERAS versus Traditional Care

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To compare opioid use, pain score & post-operative ileus on ERAS vs. traditional care after RC (Xu et al., 2015)	Study design: Retrospective Study IDV: ERAS & traditional care DV: Opioid use, pain score, Post op ileus	Sample = 205 pts. ERAS = 124; Traditional care = 81. Setting: University hospital in Los Angeles, CA	Opioid use = Morphine equivalent in milligrams (mg). Pain scale (VAS) Post-operative Ileus (%)	ERAS group used less opioid per day (4.9 mg vs. 20.67) mg Morphine equivalents ($p < .001$) ERAS group has more pain vs. traditional care VAS, 3.1 vs. 1.14 ($p < .001$) Lesser incidence of post-op ileus in ERAS vs. Traditional care (7.3% vs. 22.2%, $p = .003$). ERAS = shorter LOS (4 vs. 8 days, $p < .001$).	The post-operative pain mgmt. after and use of ERAS led to significant ↓ narcotic use & ↓ incidence of post-operative ileus compared to control group.

Table 13

Components of ERAS: Urinary Drainage / Ureteral Stents Reduces Post-Operative Morbidity

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To investigate the effect of stenting the uretero-enteric anastomosis on post-operative stricture rate & gastrointestinal recovery in urinary diversions (Mullins et al., 2011).	<p>Study Design: Retrospective Study</p> <p>IV: Stented group & Non-stented group continent urinary diversions</p> <p>: Stented and non-stented incontinent urinary diversions</p> <p>DV: ↓post-op ileus : post-op stricture rate : GI recovery : LOS</p>	<p>Sample = 192 pts. Post-radical cystectomy and continent or incontinent urinary diversions</p> <p>Setting: Pennsylvania, PA University hospital</p>	<p>Post-op stricture rate (%)</p> <p>GI recovery/post-op ileus (%)</p> <p>LOS (days)</p>	<p>Stented = 36 % Not stented = 64 %</p> <p>At time of urinary diversion</p> <p>Total ureteral stricture rate = 9.9% No statistical significance in stented vs. non-stented grp ($p = .11$)</p> <p>No statistical significance in LOS ($p = .08$) in stented vs. non-stented pts.</p> <p>↑ rate of ileus in non – stented pts (19%) vs. Stented pts (6%) POI ($p = .014$).</p>	<p>Stenting of uretero-enteric anastomosis = no effect on stricture rate but is a/w lower rate of post-op ileus.</p> <p>Limitations: Non-randomized retrospective analysis. Intra-op decisions to place stents made by surgeons. Urinary ascites not documented by sending drain fluid for creatinine analysis.</p> <p>Difference in ileus rate b/w stented & non-stented can't be associated with urinary leak.</p>

Note: BM = Bowel Movement; CR = Conservative Regimen; CV = Cardiovascular; COMP = Complication; CG = Control group; DVT = Deep Vein Thrombosis; DV = Dependent variable; DVT = Deep vein thrombosis; EBL = Estimated Blood Loss; EC = Exclusion criteria; EORTC-European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer; ERAS = Enhanced Recovery After Surgery; GI = Gastro-Intestinal; IC = Infectious Colitis; IDV = Independent variable; HS = Hospital Stay; IC = Inclusion criteria; IG = Intervention Group; INCU = Intermediate Care Unit; LMWH = Low Molecular Weight Heparin; LOS = Length of Stay; MA = Meta-analysis; MRP = Multi-Disciplinary Rehabilitation; N/V = Nausea/Vomiting; OP = Operative Method; ORC = Open Radical Cystectomy;

PCA = Patient Controlled Analgesia; PE = Pulmonary embolism; PEP = Primary End Point PHI = Pre-habilitation Intervention; PI = Paralytic Ileus; POD = Post-operative day; POI = Post-operative ileus; POM = Post-Operative Morbidity PONV = Post-Operative Nausea and Vomiting; PT = Patient; QOL = Quality of Life RA = Readmission; RARC = Robotic Assisted Radical Cystectomy; RC = Radical Cystectomy; RCT = Randomized Controlled Trial; SEP = Secondary End Point; SF-36 = Short Form Survey Scoring; SR = Systemic review; TBM = Time to Bowel Movement; TTF = Time to Flatus; UFH = Unfractionated Heparin; VTE = Venous thromboembolism; WH = Wound Healing; WHO = World Health Organization.

